

D4.5 Perceived Effectiveness of Rural Interventions, 12 Regions

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Contact:	info@polirural.eu	
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Contributing:	KAJO, HAMK	
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Acronyms and abbreviations

AEA	agri-environment agreement
BE	Belgium
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
COVID-19	coronavirus disease 2019
CZ	Czech Republic
D1.1	Deliverable 1.1
D1.7	Deliverable 1.7
D4.1	Deliverable 4.1
D4.2	Deliverable 4.2
D4.4	Deliverable 4.4
DG Regio	The European Commission's Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy
EC	European Commission
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ES	Spain
EU	European Union
EUROSTAT	European Statistical Office
FI	Finland
GR	Greece
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IE	Ireland
IL	Israel
LAG	Local Action Group
LGO	Local Governmental Organisation
LV	Latvia
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
NM	Northern Macedonia
NUTS	Nomenclature des unités territoriales statistiques
PL	Poland
SK	Slovakia
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
T4.5	Task 4.5
WP4	Work Package 4

Executive Summary

This report at hand provides a synthesis of the evaluation work that has been carried out within WP4. It offers a comparative analytical view on the evaluation results that have been prepared for the 12 pilots in the PoliRural project. Each evaluation was conducted on basis of a common methodological framework (see Annex 5) to bring forward comparable results that could inform the further work in this project.

First the pilots are grouped based on (A) types of intervention area and (B) geographical clustering, the needs are summarized and each intervention area and pilot region is discussed based on a set of characteristics. Then a comparative analysis of the evaluation results by evaluation criteria (effectiveness, relevance, and coherence) is performed and complemented by a comparative view on text-mining and sentiment analysis. Further factors that support or hamper regional development in the pilot regions are discussed, and finally conclusions based on the analyses are drawn.

The policy measures evaluated, involved the main stakeholders of the regions to tackle their policy challenges, and to promote an integrated and participative approach in their regions. Seven out of twelve policy measures are being implemented through the LEADER program.

All selected measures define their objectives to add value in the pillars considered key to make their territories more attractive. The impact has been in most cases limited, and it should increase in the future. All policy measures present their objectives clearly, and some of them show a clear breakdown of planned activities / actions / projects.

All regions have communication and dissemination mechanisms in place to communicate their objectives and achievements, although some fail to involve civil society, and potential beneficiaries in a proactive way. Also, it can be observed that the regions do not monitor or evaluate their progress in a holistic way.

All regions have identified the coherence of their measures with other policies at regional or national levels, but a more strategic and systematic coordination between regional and local governments is needed.

Keywords

Regions, Policy Measures, Evaluation, Synthesis, Survey, Text-Mining

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of evaluation and objectives

This report at hand provides a synthesis of the evaluation work that has been carried out within WP4. It offers a comparative analytical view on the evaluation results that have been prepared for the 12 pilots in the PoliRural project. Each evaluation was conducted on basis of a common methodological framework (see Annex 5) to bring forward comparable results that could inform the further work in this project.

Accordingly, T4.5 has the following objectives:

- To provide a common analytical framework for the comparative analysis of the results of evaluation field work in each pilot.
- To assess the effectiveness, relevance, and coherence of the selected policy measures in a comparative way, and
- To draw general conclusions of these findings for future rural regional policy
- To inform D1.7 Rural Attractiveness: Post-Evaluation Update
- To evaluate the adequacy and value added of text mining in policy evaluation based on the field test conducted within WP4

1.2 Overview of sections

This report comprises eight content related sections that can be briefly introduced as follows:

- **Section 2** describes the socio-economics context of the pilot regions and proposes grouping based on a cluster analysis of regional data.
- **Section 3** summarizes the needs.
- In **Section 4** the pilots are grouped based on (A) types of intervention area and (B) geographical clustering.
- **Section 5** discusses a set of characteristics for each intervention area and pilot region
- **Section 6** offers a comparative analysis of the evaluation results by evaluation criteria (effectiveness, relevance, and coherence).
- **Section 7** provides a comparative view on text-mining and sentiment analysis, by discussing results of topic extraction, sentiment analysis and assessment of this tool by the pilots.
- **Section 8** analyses, based on the surveys and interviews conducted in the pilot regions, the factors that support or hamper regional development.
- **Section 9** then draws conclusions based on the results of the sections 2 to 8 and the individual Pilot Evaluation Reports.

1.3 Methodological limitations

The reading of this report should be done with the following methodological limitations in mind:

First, it must be noted that the evaluation work implemented under T4.5 has not been intended to substitute compulsory evaluation studies on EC policy interventions (e.g., CAP, EARDF etc.). Each pilot has worked on assessing selected policy measures. Furthermore, the available resources for each pilot have been limited and thus the results will certainly not come close to a fully-fledged evaluation study performed on the basis of a contract by professionals.

Second, the synthesis of the individual results is made difficult by the fact, that it was not possible to select a specific measure common to all regions. The selection of the policy measure to be evaluated has been based on every pilot's needs/focus following the work in D4.4 (Needs-Policy Canvas).

Third, it must be noted that the teams in the individual pilot regions have shown very different levels of knowledge and experience with regard to the implementation of evaluation projects. Albeit all partners have received training and support by means of webinars and individual coaching a large heterogeneity in quality and informative value of the individual evaluation reports has to be taken into account.

Fourth, major differences in fieldwork between the pilot regions make a comparative analysis of the results difficult. This concern, on the one hand, the field work methodology chosen; while the majority of pilot regions conducted surveys, there are also regions that collected data primarily by means of interviews. On the other hand, the number of respondents also varies considerably between the individual regions.

Fifth, the use of text-mining for policy evaluation studies is still in its nascent stage. To date, the number of text mining applications in evaluation studies remains very limited (UN Global Pulse, 2016). Text mining provides in particular a methodological tool to cope with the abundance of digital information by enabling evaluators to efficiently analyse large document collections. It combines a qualitative appraisal of meaning and complex statistical approaches to extract relevant information from text (DEval Policy Brief 1/2019). While sentiment analysis is currently successfully applied such domains as market research (Stützer 2020), recent literature does not provide evidence for its successful application in evaluation field work. Topic modelling could be in comparison applied fruitfully to investigate the causes of successful policy interventions for evaluation studies (DEval Policy Brief 1/2019). The efficient exploration of large collections of evaluation reports by extracting references to influential topics such as political institutions or economic performance (idem.).

Finally, it is noteworthy that that survey results have been based on subjective judgements of respondents, thus the assessment of the three evaluation criteria 'effectiveness', 'relevance', and 'coherence' is to be seen as a result of the analysis of perceptions of the respondents of the survey or interview.

2 Context of the pilots

It is well-known (see D4.1 and D 4.4.) that there are significant differences among the pilot regions. This chapter aims to analyse this diversity and proposes a classification of pilot regions (EU) that is adjusted to the different axes of socioeconomic development and, simultaneously, is useful for basis of comprehensive, multi-source, multi-method evaluation of rural interventions in the regions.

2.1 The pilots in a nutshell

The twelve pilot regions are distributed across Europe and beyond, Figure 1 displays the name and country of each PoliRural pilot region, and also its spatial location.

Figure 1 Spatial location of PoliRural pilot regions

A brief overview of the socio-economic characteristics of the PoliRural pilot regions is presented in Table 1 below.

Pilot Region and NUTS Level (covered in the further analysis)	Socio-economic characteristics
Pilot 1 Flanders, Belgium (NUTS 1: BE2)	Flanders is the northern region of Belgium. Flanders covers 44.5% of Belgium's territory and represents the majority of the country's industry and workforce; the region provides 60.1% of the national gross domestic product (GDP) (Eurostat, 2020). The region has a very high population density (475 inhabitants per km ²) which is more than four times the average density of the European Union. Only 7% of the area is rural and 2.5% of the population lives in the rural area. With high land pressures, agriculture in Flanders (Belgium) is highly industrialised. Agriculture and rural development is under regional responsibility in Belgium. In Flanders there are several institutions responsible for agriculture governance.
Pilot 2 Monaghan, Ireland (NUTS 2: IE04)	County Monaghan is a mainly rural county in the Republic of Ireland, on the border with Northern Ireland which is in the UK. County Monaghan is the fifth smallest of the Irish Republic's 26 counties in area (1295km ²) and fourth smallest by population (61,386), with 63.2% of the county's population living in a rural area (Eurostat 2020). Agriculture is a significant part of the County Monaghan economy, employing about 12.1% of the population in 2017 (compared with 5% nationally). Monaghan County Council is the local authority for the county. However, most agriculture and rural development policies and programmes are centrally driven and funded by Ireland's Government and the EU. The LEADER programme supports many local projects in County Monaghan.
Pilot 3 Segobriga, Spain (NUTS 2: ES42)	Segobriga is located in the centre of Spain in the municipality of Saelices, in the region Castilla-La Mancha. The region covers an area of 79,463 km ² , which in 2018 was home to 2,034,877 inhabitants, representing approximately 4.3% of the country's population (Eurostat, 2020). Main socio-economic strengths include a declining unemployment rate (although still as high as 9%), an important agriculture sector (employs 7.26% of the active population and contributes 8.1% to Gross Value Added (GVA)). The region's development is rather behind that of the rest of Spain, but recent positive growth points to first signs of recovery after the economic crisis. The main economic activity of Segobriga is agricultural production connected to a large share of the industrial sector in the area. This territory is characterized by presenting a poorly diversified economy based on agriculture with low added value. 94.69% of the UAA (utilised agricultural area), is oriented to the production of extensive crops (cereals and oil seeds) and permanent crops, olive oil (2.11%) and wine (3.11%). There are few agri-food industries, although it has a strong qualitative importance (e.g.: Designation of Origin "Miel de la Alcarria"). The commercial sector is complementary to rural tourism, although it is also very limited. On the other hand, historical and cultural heritage is one of the great assets of the territory, which makes tourism a strategic development axis.
Pilot 4 Vidzeme, Latvia (NUTS 2: LV00)	Planning Region Vidzeme (VPR) lies in the North East of Latvia. This region is the biggest planning region in Latvia, it covers 15,257 km ² or 24% of the country's' territory. The largest area in the region is covered by forest – currently 52% with an increasing tendency over the last years. Agricultural land covers around 34% of the territory (Eurostat, 2020). The number of population in the region is around 240 thousand. Agriculture keeps a strategic position in the Latvian economy and employment structure, especially in rural areas. The Rural Development Programme for 2014-2020 initially proposed measures to better target (specifically) small farms, but they have been reduced. Meanwhile, policy and planning documents for the next planning

Pilot Region and NUTS Level (covered in the further analysis)	Socio-economic characteristics
	period (2021-2027) show a turning point in Rural Development by highlighting the necessity of diversification of rural economy and integrated territorial development.
Pilot 5 Mazowieckie, Poland (NUTS 2: PL92)	Rural areas account for about 93% of Poland's surface area and comprise almost 40% of the country's population. Rural areas are characterised by great diversity in terms of both the state of the natural environment and the level of social and economic development. One of the basic features of the rural settlement network is a high degree of fragmentation. Looking at the most important key indicators of the Mazowieckie region, its gross domestic product (GDP) was estimated to be €25,63bn in 2018, which equalled 5.1% of the national GDP, and which gave it the 13th place among the Polish regions. The GDP per capita was € 18,400, equalling 84.4% of the national average (Eurostat, 2020). The unemployment rate of the region was 4.6% in 2019, which was above the national average of 3.3% (Central Statistical Office, 2019. Regions of Poland Report, 2019).
Pilot 6 Central Bohemia, Czech Republic (NUTS 2: CZ05)	Central Bohemia region (Střední Čechy) is the largest region in the Czech Republic (CZ) with a population of 1.37m inhabitants, accounting for 12.9% of the country's total population (Eurostat, 2020). The position of the region and its close proximity to the capital city positively affects the economic development and prosperity of the region. A good transportation network makes the region an important source of labour force for Prague. The main industries in the region are automotive and its suppliers, engineering, chemical industry and food industry. The Czech Republic was one of the first countries to agree on a Rural Development Programme, under which funding may primarily be drawn by farmers, food producers, owners and tenants of forest land and municipalities.
Pilot 7 Slovakia (NUTS 0: SK)	Based on a new typology of rural areas developed by the European Commission (Eurostat), Slovakia is 50.3% prevailing in predominantly rural areas, 38.4% in transitional areas and 11.2% in predominantly urban areas (Eurostat, 2020). Of the total area of the SR according to individual types of regions, the largest share is 59%, also in predominantly rural area, 36.8% share is in transition regions, and the lowest share- 4.2% is predominantly in urban regions. Total rural regions thus account for 95.8% of the territory of the country. Behalf of these facts, the SK pilot includes whole Slovakia as single region.
Pilot 8 Häme, Finland (NUTS 2: FI1C)	Häme Pilot region locates in the southern part of Finland and most of the region is classified as rural area close to urban area. According to Eurostat (2020), in 2018 regional gross domestic product (GDP) was €43.88bn in Häme, which represents 18.7% of national GDP. Agriculture, the food industry and food trade are of great importance to employment and the regional economy in the regions of Häme (Kanta-Häme and Päijät-Häme). 16% of the population is employed in the food chain. The food chain's net sales were € 1.4 bn. in Kanta-Häme and € 1.5 bn. in Päijät-Häme. Indirectly, the food sector employs most in services, traffic, trade and construction. Due to the structural change on agriculture, forestry and industry, their role as an employer has decreased in Häme Pilot Region. At the same time, the service industry, tourism, wellbeing, building and maintenance services have increased.
Pilot 9 Central Greece, Greece (NUTS 2: EL64)	The region of Central Greece -Sterea Ellada (capital: Lamia), with a total area of 15,549.31 km ² and a population of 555,960 inhabitants (2019), is located at the heart of Greece (Eurostat, 2020). The region is characterised by geographical and economic heterogeneity, with urban areas being more developed than the rural and mountainous zones with high unemployment rate, however it has been decreasing and in 2019 was at 17.2% (Eurostat, 2020), as compared to 18.9% in

Pilot Region and NUTS Level (covered in the further analysis)	Socio-economic characteristics
	<p>2018, and a figure significantly lower compared to the 2013 level (28.2%). The region is characterised by a highly variable landscape, possessing some of the most fertile agricultural plains in the country. Central Greece is strongly specialised in the agriculture sector. The agricultural sector in Greece is characterised by one of the highest proportions of small-scale family farms in Europe. Over half of the country's 709.500 agricultural holdings have less than 2 hectares and the small and fragmented land parcels constitute one of the main characteristics of Greek agriculture. In terms of employment, agriculture accounts for 12% and the agri-food sector for 4% of the total. The economic importance of the sector is therefore significant and enhancing its competitiveness by overcoming its structural, environmental and climatic limitations remains a key challenge.</p>
Pilot 10 Apulia, Italy (NUTS 2: ITF4)	<p>Apulia is the easternmost region of all Italy and is located in the South and is the eighth largest region by demographic size. The local institutional set-up comprises six provinces and 258 municipalities. The resident population is 4,029,053 inhabitants with a population density of 206.2 inhabitants per km². Apulia lags behind the national and European economies in terms of economic development. GDP per capita in PPS was on average €19,300 in 2018, among the lowest in the country related to the national GDP per capita (€29,700) and the GDP per capita for EU (€31,000), (Eurostat, 2020). Apulian agriculture is characterized by a strong variety of production situations. Apulia is one of the Italian regions with the most hectares of utilized agricultural area (UAA), equal to 65.8% of the overall regional area and 10.2% of the national UAA93. The food sector has always been one of the strongest areas of the Apulian economy.</p>
Pilot 11 Gevgelija-Strumica, North Macedonia	<p>Macedonia, whose name officially changed in January 2019 to become North Macedonia, is the poorest of the former Yugoslav republics; however, it has made significant progress in expanding its economy over the past decade. After a growth of 2.7% in 2018, the economy accelerated to an estimated 3.6% in 2019, supported by domestic demand which benefited from a rise in the minimum wage (which involved almost one third of the workforce). The Republic of North Macedonia (formerly known as FYROM) has been traditionally based on agriculture. The agricultural sector represents 7.2% of the GDP and employs 16% of the active population (World Bank, 2019). Arable agricultural land accounts for half of the total territory, of which about two-thirds is categorised as pastures, and the rest as arable agricultural land. The country mainly produces grapes, tobacco, vegetables and fruits.</p>
Pilot 12 Galilee, Israel	<p>Galilee is a peripheral, verdant region of rolling hills and rich agricultural valleys. With most of the population of the Region living in small towns and villages, accessibility—both intra-regional and between rural and urban areas—is challenging. Growing population, Israel is a young society compared to the western economies, a primary driver for this age structure is the high fertility rate in Israel. The age structure varies with type of locality as the rural population tends to have more children and a younger age structure.</p>

Table 1 Socio Economic overview of the pilot regions

2.2 Clustering of pilots by their level of socio-economic development

To look at the pilots in their socio-economic context we classified them into three clusters according to their development. Multivariate statistical techniques allowed us the identification of clusters of socioeconomic similarity. The socioeconomic variables considered in the study

were selected from the Eurostat Database “Regio” NUTS3 level, as well as from the Regional Competitiveness Index (RCI) and from the Regional Innovation Scoreboard (see Table 8 in Annex 1).

To search for groups of pilots (regions) different agglomerative hierarchical clustering procedures were carried out, involving the scores of the factors referred to in Table 8. To define the clusters, we used complete-linkage clustering as one of several methods of agglomerative hierarchical clustering¹. At the beginning of the process, each element is in a cluster of its own. The clusters are then sequentially combined into larger clusters until all elements end up being in the same cluster.

Figure 2 Dendrogram of pilot region cluster

The result of the clustering can be visualized as a dendrogram displayed in Figure 2, which shows the sequence of cluster fusion and the distance at which each fusion took place. According to their socio-economic development we have grouped the regions into three

¹ The method is also known as farthest neighbour clustering.

clusters: **Cluster 1** contains pilot regions with strong socio-economic growth, like Flanders in Belgium (BE) and Häme in Finland (FI). **Cluster 2** contains pilot regions with moderate socio-economic growth like Segóbriga in Spain (ES) and Apulia in Italy (IT). **Cluster 3** contains Central Greece, Monaghan in Ireland (IE), Central Bohemia in the Czech Republic (CZ), Mazowieckie in Poland (PL), Vidzeme in Latvia (LV) and Slovakia as regions with socio-economic growth on smaller scale. **Cluster 4** comprises the regions not belonging to EU territory (i.e., Gevgelija-Strumica in North Macedonia (NM) and Galilee in Israel (IL)). It was found that each of the main groups of the pilot regions differ not only in socioeconomic strengths but also in other indicators associated with their particular weaknesses.

The descriptive statistics shown in Table 9 (see Annex 1) reflect some huge asymmetries between the pilots. The most remarkable one is population density. As for demography, the differences in potentially active population or in the percentage of aged population are also significant.

3 Needs

The rural areas participating in the project start from different situations and realities but share common needs because they all want to achieve one goal: to visualize more attractive rural places and professions in their territory. This chapter shows **the needs that have been addressed in the group of measures selected by the pilots for evaluation**. The sources of information used for its identification were the Policy Canvas D4.4 document and the profile of the selected policy measure (Annex 5).

The needs addressed have been grouped into 7 pillars, as well as those used for the collection of needs in (D1.1 and D4.2). The following table shows the relationship between the pillars and the policy measure selected by the pilots for the assessment. The name of the region has been highlighted to identify which pillars the evaluated policy measure focuses on (see table 2).

Pilot Region	Key Internal Success Factors
1. Availability of public and other services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apulia (IT) • Segóbriga (ES) • Central Bohemian (CZ) • Galilee (IL) • Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) • Vidzeme (LV) • Slovakia
2. Recreational and social activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None
3. Living conditions and quality of life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apulia (IT) • Central Greece • Central Bohemia (CZ) • Galilee (IL)
4. Demographics and Human capital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Segóbriga (ES) • Häme (FI) • Central Bohemia (CZ) • Apulia (IT)

Pilot Region	Key Internal Success Factors
5. Business Economy and Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flanders (BE) • Monaghan (IE) • Segóbriga (ES) • Central Bohemia (CZ) • Häme (FI) • Central Greece • Galilee (IL) • Apulia (IT) • Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) • Mazowieckie (PL) • Slovakia • Vidzeme (LV)
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Central Bohemia (CZ) • Segobrina (ES)
7. Environment and biodiversity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flanders (BE) • Monaghan (IE) • Central Bohemia (CZ) • Apulia (IT) • Slovakia

Table 2 Relation between pillars and policy measure selected by the pilots for the evaluation

The needs that are addressed in the selected measures are described below for each of the pillars.

Pillar 1: Availability of public and other services:

- Encourage the creation or reconstruction of infrastructure connections between rural and urban areas, therefore towards the main city of the region, with particular attention to transportation to health services.
- Need to establish integrated health and social care (especially related to aging population,
- Guarantee sufficient and quality services (nurseries, electricity, drinking water, commercial services, fairgrounds, waste treatment services, etc.).
- Guarantee quality access to internet broadband connection in the territory and improve the training of the population in the use of the internet and telematics services.
- Need to ensure accessibility of services for all inhabitants of the region.

Pillar 3: Living conditions and quality of life:

- Promote social inclusion and improve the quality of life of disadvantaged people.
- Need to have sustainable settlements; regions and landscape in the context of climate change; improving access to drinking water, sewerage and clean resources available, sustainable urban development, preventing climate change and, last but not least, protecting terrestrial life.

Pillar 4: Demographics and Human capital:

- Encourage vocational and higher education, and training, particularly for youth and women.

- Inventing ways to get young people to live and work in the region. There is a need to **support young people** to return to the region.
- Avoid the exodus of young people and women from the territory and fight against depopulation.

Pillar 5: **Business Economy and Innovation:**

- Promote the **employment of women and young people**.
- Encourage the **creation of new businesses and support youth and women** entrepreneurship and the birth of innovative start-ups.
- Need to strengthen the **cooperation between education and business**.
- Need for boosting the attractiveness of the region for tourism and agri-tourism. Promote economic **diversification** in a jointly organized way from the institutions and the private sector, through the **touristic development** of the area, taking advantage of the heritage and natural resources existing in the territory, correctly defining a tourist package as well as promoting a complementary offer.
- Stimulate the profitability of the agricultural sector and promoting the diversification of the regional economy. Promoting the **development of agribusiness** from existing raw materials, especially cereals with transformation, commercialization, organic products, local market, etc.
- Promote **employment niches related to the circular economy**, among others.
- Encourage more **sustainable agriculture**, production of vegetables and forestry development.
- Provide support **schemes that encourage new entrants** into farming.
- **Support farmers** and encourage young and new farmers.
- Creating a business-friendly environment.
- Need to establish new high-tech/innovative companies and their connection with research organizations, support of developing start-ups and spin-off companies.
- Need to attract young professionals to work in high-tech/innovative companies and research organizations located in the region.
- The need to promote local production by supporting local products and local producers can be significantly strengthened through improved, stronger and better implementation of the EU Quality Policy in Slovakia.

Pillar 6: **Social and cultural aspects of rural areas:**

- Enhance and ensure the heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g., small landscape elements).
- Need to support the local identity to sustain the proper development of all areas of the region.
- Facilitate newcomers to be adopted into the community.
- Increase initiatives and organized actions for promotion (publicity, marketing activities and projects, agri-tourism) and effective exploitation of high natural and historical value areas.

Pillar 7: Environment and biodiversity:

- Enhance and ensure the heritage and patrimony of rural areas, rural landscape as cultural heritage (e.g., small landscape elements).
- Find a balance between nature and agriculture in a highly fragmented rural landscape.
- Climate smart and innovative agriculture: agricultural sector needs to deal with the challenges and opportunities related with climate change e.g., drought.
- Encourage more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables & forestry development.
- Need for adaptation to the climate change.
- Need for transition to the circular economy and bioeconomy.
- Promote technological innovation linked to the Green and Circular Economy.

All the selected policy measures address needs in the area of pillar 5: economic activity and innovation. Seven of the policy measures have shown needs related to pillar 1: Availability of public and other services. Five also address needs related to pillar 7: Environment and biodiversity. Four with pillar 3: Living conditions and quality of life and pillar 4: Demographics and Human capital. And two with pillar 6: Social and cultural aspects of rural areas and none related to pillar 2: Recreational and social activities.

The most present pillar is that of Business Economy and Innovation. This can be explained by the fact that measures in these domains provide opportunities for combinations with other policy domains, such as environment and biodiversity, demographics and human capital, availability of public services and others.

4 Grouping of pilots

The pilots are grouped based on (A) types of intervention area and (B) geographical clustering.

4.1 Geographical Clustering

Following section 2 of this report, geographical grouping leads to four distinct clusters that are largely related to their level of socio-economic development. The exception is the two regions — Gevgelija-Strumica and Galilee — outside of the EU (Table 3).

Regions with high socio-economic development level	Regions with moderate socio-economic development level	Regions with low socio-economic development level	Non-EU Pilots
Flanders (BE)	Segóbriga (ES)	Vidzeme (LV)	Gevgelija-Strumica (NM)
Häme (FI)	Apulia (IT)	Monaghan (IE)	Galilee (IL)
		Central Greece	
		Mazowieckie (PL)	

Regions with high socio-economic development level	Regions with moderate socio-economic development level	Regions with low socio-economic development level	Non-EU Pilots
		Slovakia	
		Central Bohemia (CZ))	

Table 3 Grouping of pilot regions based on socio-economic clusters

4.2 Brief characterization of policies by pillar

Pilot regions have indicated the policy measures in their pilots (see table 4). By cross-referencing these policy measures with the pillars, an overview of policy measures per pillar can be generated. Note that most pilot regions have indicated multiple pillars.

Pillar	Pilot Region	Type of intervention	Policy Measures
1. Availability of public and other services	A. Apulia (IT) B. Segóbriga (ES) C. Central Bohemia (CZ) D. Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) E. Slovakia F. Vidzeme (LV)	A. Non-Financial B. Financial and non-financial C. Non-Financial D. Financial E. Non-Financial and regulatory F. Non-Financial	A. implementation and promotion of Local Development Strategies B. development and implementation of a regional Country Plan C. Development of a regional development strategy D. Investments in infrastructure for development E. Regulations to increase competitiveness by EU Quality Policy F. promote public involvement in local economic strengthening initiatives
2. Recreational and social activities			
3. Living conditions and quality of life	A. Apulia (IT)	A. Non-Financial	A. implementation and promotion of Local Development Strategies
4. Demographics and Human capital	A. Segóbriga (ES) B. Häme (FI) C. Central Bohemia (CZ) D. Central Greece	A. Financial and non-financial B. Financial C. Non-Financial D. Financial and non-financial	A. development and implementation of a Regional Country Plan B. supporting new and growing business opportunities in farms and rural areas C. Development of a regional development strategy D. development of capacities for employment and diversification in rural areas
5. Business Economy and Innovation	A. Flanders (BE) B. Monaghan (IE) C. Segóbriga (ES) D. Central Bohemia (CZ) E. Häme (FI) F. Central Greece G. Apulia (IT)	A. Financial B. Financial and non-financial C. Financial and non-financial D. Non-Financial E. Financial F. Financial and non-financial	A. financial compensation for environmental / biodiversity measures B. implementation of Local Development Strategy - Environmental Theme C. development and implementation of a regional Country Plan D. Development of a regional development strategy

Pillar	Pilot Region	Type of intervention	Policy Measures
	H. Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) I. Mazowieckie (PL) J. Slovakia K. Vidzeme (LV)	G. Non-Financial H. Financial I. Financial J. Non-Financial and regulatory K. Non-Financial	E. supporting new and growing business opportunities in farms and rural areas F. development of capacities for employment and diversification in rural areas G. implementation and promotion of Local Development Strategies H. Investments in infrastructure for development I. grants to set up or develop a business J. Regulations to increase competitiveness by EU Quality Policy K. promote public involvement in local economic strengthening initiatives
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	A. Central Bohemia (CZ) B. Häme (FI) C. Flanders (BE) D. Central Greece	A. Non-Financial B. Financial C. Financial D. Financial and non-financial	A. Development of a regional development strategy B. supporting new and growing business opportunities in farms and rural areas C. financial compensation for environmental / biodiversity measures D. development of capacities for employment and diversification in rural areas
7. Environment and biodiversity	A. Flanders (BE) B. Monaghan (IE) C. Central Bohemia (CZ) D. Apulia (IT) E. Slovakia	A. Financial B. Financial and non-financial C. Non-Financial D. Non-Financial E. Non-Financial and regulatory	A. financial compensation for environmental / biodiversity measures B. implementation of Local Development Strategy - Environmental Theme C. Development of a regional development strategy D. implementation and promotion of Local Development Strategies E. Regulations to increase competitiveness by EU Quality Policy

Table 4 Policy measures per pillar

Table 3 shows that types of intervention in the pilot regions were both financial and non-financial and in some pilot regions, both types were used. A range of different policy measures were taken, depending on the pillar and goals for each region. Development and/or implementation of a development strategy / regional plan / economic strategy is mentioned in most reports. Investments in infrastructure development and environmental diversity are also mentioned as policy measures in some cases.

5 Characterisation of policies in each group

Table 5 shows a set of characteristics for each pillar and pilot region (based on Table 4). The total project funding differs from € 5 m. to € 158 m.; with about half of the project funds are in the € 5-7 m. range. Total funding of two pilot regions is unclear from the report (Flanders and Central Bohemia).

Beneficiaries range from farmers, SMEs, community groups, government bodies to NGOs. In most pilot regions, there is a mixed set of public and private beneficiaries that reap the benefits of the projects. In some cases, only farmers can apply for funding.

There is a big spread between the number of projects in each pilot region, depending on the scope and nature of the evaluated topic.

About half of the pilot regions are close to finalising the projects or have finalised already, in the other half the projects are still ongoing. The continuation of the project is uncertain or unclear in about half of the pilot cases, while in two cases a new program has been installed or advised.

Pillar	Pilot Region	Funding (total)	Beneficiaries	# Projects	Status	Continuation
1. Availability of public and other services	A. Apulia (IT) B. Segóbriga (ES) C. Central Bohemia (CZ) D. Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) E. Slovakia F. Vidzeme (LV)	A. € 158.849.586 B. € 7.537.598 C. Unclear* D. € 28.670.549 E. unclear* F. € 7.952.566	A. Local action groups, local actors B. SMEs, Small Agroindustry, Local C. SMEs, Small Agroindustry, Local Entities, Associations, Farmers, NGOs D. Public enterprises + municipalities E. unclear F. SME's and entrepreneurs	A. 764 projects B. 66 projects C. 1 project D. 202 projects E. 12 projects F. 409 projects	A. ongoing B. ongoing C. Finalised D. close to ending E. ongoing F. 40% implemented	A. Uncertain B. Continuation advised C. Pending E. unclear* F. Ongoing
2. Rec. Soc. activities						
3. Living conditions and quality of life	A. Apulia (IT)	A. € 158.849.586	A. Local action groups, local actors	A. 764 projects	A. ongoing	A. Uncertain
4. Demographics and Human capital	A. Segóbriga (ES) B. Häme (FI) C. Central Bohemia (CZ) D. Central Greece	A. € 7.537.598 B. € 5.538.462 C. Unclear* D. € 5.527.500	A. SMEs, Small Agroindustry, Local Entities, Associations, Farmers, NGOs B. SMEs, NGOs C. SMEs, Small Agroindustry, Local Entities, Associations, Farmers, NGOs D. private farmers, businesses, NGOs, local government, LGOs	A. 66 projects B. Unclear * C. 1 project D. 37 projects	A. ongoing B. 90% implemented C. Finalised D. ongoing	A. Continuation advised B. unclear* C. Pending D. 26 projects transferred

Pillar	Pilot Region	Funding (total)	Beneficiaries	# Projects	Status	Continuation
5. Business Economy and Innovation	A. Flanders (BE) B. Monaghan (IE) C. Segóbriga (ES) D. Central Bohemia (CZ) E. Häme (FI) F. Central Greece G. Apulia (IT) H. Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) I. Mazowieckie (PL) J. Slovakia K. Vidzeme (LV)	A. unclear* B. €7.590.000 C. € 7.537.598 D. unclear* E. € 5.538.462 F. € 5.527.500 G. € 158.849.586 H. € 28.670.549 I. € 6.333.622** J. unclear* K. € 7.952.566	A. Registered farmers B. community groups, SME, social enterprises C. SMEs, Small Agroindustry, Local Entities, Associations, Farmers, NGOs D. Regional government E. SMEs, NGOs F. private farmers, businesses, NGOs, local government, LGOs G. Local action groups, local actors H. Public enterprises + municipalities I. entrepreneurs, SMEs and citizens J. unclear K. SME's and entrepreneurs	A. 3823 farmers B. unclear * C. 66 projects D. 1 project E. Unclear* F. 37 project G. 764 projects H. 202 projects I. 53 projects J. 12 projects K. 409 projects	A. unclear* B. 90% implemented C. ongoing D. Finalised E. 90% implemented F. ongoing G. ongoing H. close to ending I. 86% implemented J. ongoing K. 40% implemented	A. Unclear* B. Replaced by new program C. Continuation advised D. Pending E. Unclear* F. 26 project transferred G. Uncertain H. I. ongoing J. unclear* K. Ongoing
6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas	A. Central Bohemia (CZ) B. Häme (FI) C. Flanders (BE) D. Central Greece	A. Unclear* B. € 5.527.500 C. Unclear* D. € 5.527.500	A. Regional government B. SMEs, NGOs C. Registered farmers D. private farmers, businesses, NGOs, local government, LGOs	A. 1 project B. Unclear* C. 3823 farmers D. 37 projects	A. Finalised B. 90% implemented C. unclear * D. ongoing	A. Pending B. unclear* C. unclear* D. 26 projects transferred
7. Environment and biodiversity	A. Flanders (BE) B. Monaghan (IE) C. Central Bohemia (CZ) D. Apulia (IT) E. Slovakia	A. Unclear* B. €7.590.000 C. Unclear* D. € 158.849.586 E. € 6.333.622**	A. Registered farmers B. community groups, SME, social enterprises C. Regional government D. Local action groups, local actors E. unclear	A. 3823 farmers B. unclear * C. 37 projects D. 764 projects E. 12 projects	A. unclear* B. 90% implemented C. Finalised D. ongoing E. ongoing	A. unclear* B. replaced by new program C. Pending D. Uncertain E. unclear

Table 5 Characterisation of policies in each group

*Unclear from report

** Exchange rate PLN-Euro 28-01-2021 (Source: Morningstar)

6 Comparative Analysis by Evaluation Criteria

6.1 Overview

In total ten out of twelve pilots have used common survey questions in their field work. Table 6 provides a respective overview also displaying the selected policy measures and the number of respondents.

Only Flanders (BE) and Mazowieckie (PL) have used their own set of questions without including the common questions as developed in the evaluation matrix (see Annex 3). Accordingly, these two pilot regions are not included in the comparative analysis.

Pilot Region	Policy Measure	Type of field research	Number of Respondents
Flanders (BE)	Financial compensation for environmental / biodiversity measures	No use of common questions	n.a.
Monaghan (IE)	Implementation of Local Development Strategy - Environmental Theme	Survey	27
Häme (FI)	Supporting new and growing business opportunities in farms and rural areas	Interviews	13
Segóbriga (ES)	Development and implementation of a regional Country Plan	Survey	25
Apulia (IT)	Implementation and promotion of Local Development Strategies	Survey	40
Central Greece	Development of capacities for employment and diversification in rural areas	Survey	61
Vidzeme (LV)	Promote public involvement in local economic strengthening initiatives	Survey	17
Central Bohemia (CZ)	Development of a regional development strategy	Survey	6
Slovakia	Regulations to increase competitiveness by EU Quality Policy	Survey	31
Mazowieckie (PL)	Grants to set up or develop a business	No use of common questions	42
Gevgelija-Strumica (NM)	Investments in infrastructure for development	Survey	18
Galilee (IL)	Digitization of rural areas	Interviews	10

Table 6 Selected policy measures and basic field work characteristics

The comparative analysis of the three evaluation criteria synthesises the findings of the individual Pilot Evaluation Reports. In order to achieve this, a common dataset based on results of the conducted surveys and interviews has been created. The analysis is done according to the evaluation criteria relevance, effectiveness, coherence, while results are presented by type of cluster as defined in chapter 2.2.

6.2 Effectiveness of the policy measures

The evaluation of effectiveness is a measure of the progress made towards achieving the objectives of the policy measure, looking for evidence of why, whether or how these changes are attributed to the policy measure. Evaluation questions answered in this section include:

- To what extent the policy measure has achieved its objectives? Includes an evidence-based judgement of the progress made.
- What were the key success factors in achieving the objectives?
- What were the key obstacles hindering the progress?

According to the survey for evaluating the effectiveness of measures in the pilot regions, it can be concluded that most of the respondents have agreed that the measure has achieved its initial objective. The majority of respondents (in av. 75 %) in Cluster 1, 3 and 4 estimates that the goals have been achieved well or excellently (see Figure 3 and Figure 6 in Annex 2).

The effectiveness most of the regional measure must be considered in the long term. The Pilot Evaluation Reports showed that e.g. investments in the respective regions are made in the long run. The effects will be significant, but they will not be immediately visible and will even take years. Almost half of the respondents estimated that external factors affected the progress of the measure. The results vary in the individual cluster: 59 % of the pilots in Cluster 3 and 50 % of the Pilots in Cluster 2 estimated, that external factors affected the progress of the measures from a moderate high to a great extent on (see Figure 3 and Figure 9 in Annex 2).

Feedback from the stakeholders on the overall effectiveness of the policy measure in the analysed cluster in response to the survey questions were as follows, where the numbers indicate:

- 4 – “To a great extent”
- 3 – “To a moderate high extent”
- 2 – “To a moderate low extent”
- 1 – “To a small extent”
- 0 – “Not at all”

Figure 3 Perceived effectiveness of the evaluated policy measure in the Pilot Clusters

6.3 Relevance of the policy measures

Relevance refers to the evaluation question whether the objectives of the selected policy measure are still relevant or where there have been changes in the underlying problems and drivers. The assessment looks at the relationship between the needs and problems and the objectives of the policy measure. Questions answered in this section include:

- To what extent the objectives of the policy measure met the initial needs?
- How well do the original objectives correspond to the current needs?
- To what extent the policy measure is still relevant?

According to the aggregated results of the survey carried out in the pilot regions, it can be concluded that the respondents of the pilots agree to large extent that the objective of the measure is consistent with their initial needs. More than 70 % of the respondents in Cluster 1, 3 and 4 indicated that objectives of the policy measure met the initial needs well or excellently. 50 % of the respondents in Cluster 2 have answered in a similar manner (see Figure 4 and Figure 11 in Annex 2).

The results connected with the second question dealing with relevance show that the perception for the contribution of the measure is slightly different from the perception of how the measure meets the needs. More than 80 % of the respondents in cluster 1 and 4 indicated that policy measure achieved the rural policy objectives/package for the region objectives well or excellently. Only 47 % of the respondents in cluster 2 agree to large extent with the

statement expressed in the question (see also Figure 13 in Annex 2). Regarding the third question connected with relevance, respondents of the cluster 1 and 3 agree to large extent that the needs and objectives targeted by the policy measure still apply at the end of its implementation (see also Figure 15 in Annex 2). The relevancy of the policy measure in the pilot region was still high and the need for this kind of measures was seen continuous in the future.

Feedback from the stakeholders on the overall relevance of the policy measure in the selected cluster in response to the survey questions were as follows, where the numbers indicate:

- 4 – “To a great extent”
- 3 – “To a moderate high extent”
- 2 – “To a moderate low extent”
- 1 – “To a small extent”
- 0 – “Not at all”

Figure 4 Perceived relevance of the evaluated policy measure in the Pilot Clusters

6.4 Coherence of the policy measures

The evaluation of coherence assesses how well the policy measure is aligned with other local, regional, national or EU policy measures. Coherence issues proved more difficult and reserved the most “I don't know” – answers. This may be because there are several administrative bodies in charge of implementing different policy measures in the pilot regions.

This section provides answers to following questions:

- To what extent is the policy measure coherent with other policy interventions having similar objectives?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other local and regional policy measures?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant national policy measures?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant EU policy measures? E.g., CAP, LEADER, digital transformation, green deal, demographic change, etc.
- To what extent the policy measure is contributing to EU added value? (e.g., EU Regional Targets: Globalisation, climate change, energy challenge, demographic change)

The results of the survey questions dealing with coherence show that the selected policy measures are to a high degree consistent with the policy objectives and actions defined in strategic documents and programs for rural development on national, regional and local level.

The majority of the stakeholders indicated that the policy measure coherent “to a great extent” with other policy interventions having similar objectives (see Figure 5). Almost 86% of respondents in cluster 1, and the majority of cluster 3 and 4 stated that the evaluated policy measures are in line with similar policies in the pilot regions. The evaluated measures focus on rural development (see Figure 19 and Figure 17 Annex 2). Therefore, there is a strong link between other regional policy interventions and the objectives and actions in the LEADER local development strategy. The responses on the question regarding the correspondence of the measure on the current needs showed variability. The majority of the stakeholders in cluster 1 answered ‘to a great extent’. In average 40 % the respondents of cluster 2, 3 and 4 answered the same (see Figure 21 Annex 2). The vast majority of respondents agreed that the evaluated measures were coherent with other policy interventions on the local, national and European levels.

Feedback from the stakeholders on the overall coherence of the policy measure in the selected cluster in response to the survey questions were as follows, where the numbers indicate:

- 4 – “To a great extent”
- 3 – “To a moderate high extent”
- 2 – “To a moderate low extent”
- 1 – “To a small extent”
- 0 – “Not at all”

Figure 5 Perceived coherence of the evaluated policy measure in the Pilot Clusters

7 Comparative view on text-mining and sentiment analysis

For ten out of twelve pilots a text mining analysis has been conducted to complement the fieldwork based on surveys and/or interviews. The pilot from Galilee (IL) and Gevgelija-Strumica (NM) indicated already in the beginning of the fieldwork that they could not do this analysis as it was not possible to develop semantic features for these two languages because of the lack of a specific thesaurus – thus they are excluded a priori from the list.

Text mining analysis was done by each pilot for the selected policy measure that has been selected for evaluation. Text Mining (TM) to address the implementation of the selected policy measure was investigated by creating the Curated Reading List (CRL) in the Semex Reading Lists. This was then explored as described in “TM training: policy evaluation”². Analysis with the Semex tool led then to detailed results that can be consulted in the annex to this report.

Table 7 provides a systematic overview of the text-mining results per pilot. Not included is information from Mazowieckie (PL) as this pilot has to date not submitted his report on text mining.

²<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/e/1FAIpQLSebCVkC93WLu98GWAuauir2Rkvj6hr-mWWXNh2QrNwKvwCv6g/viewform>

Pilot	Most relevant topics	General tendency in observed sentiment	Topics with most negative sentiment	Supportive to the evaluation field work	Justification	Effort needed (in person days)
Flanders (BE)	biodiversity, environment, agriculture and landscape	Neutral to positive	Environment, pollution, landscape and plant species	n.a.	n.a.	2,5
Monaghan (IE)	County, local development, rural development, new community	Lightly positive	County, building service, information service, public services	Yes	Text Mining enabled a large amount of previous work and literature to be analysed to give a different perspective, with interesting insights and very useful sentiment quotes. Overall, the analysis confirms survey feedback.	1,5
Häme (FI)	Topics on displayed in Finnish language. In English from TM results; project, city centre, local recreational activities, the promotion of trade and industry, urban architecture, improving housing conditions, transportation system	Positive	city centre, promotion of trade and industry, rural habitat, association, economic sector, city service	No	Test trials didn't provide further information to the policy evaluation.	2
Segóbriga (ES)	Rural development and programs development	Neutral to positive	natural heritage, natural parks or natural monuments	Yes	The identified topics confirm that LEADER is key for the Segobriga's development and that the environment and tourism are the	6

Pilot	Most relevant topics	General tendency in observed sentiment	Topics with most negative sentiment	Supportive to the evaluation field work	Justification	Effort needed (in person days)
					most important values to be boosted, in order to achieve a sustainable growth.	
Apulia (IT)	Entire agricultural chain with the related legislation	Neutral to positive		Yes	Several topics and keywords have been identified that gave a different perspective. Indeed, mining through their ranking provides interesting insights. In general, there is no strong adherence to the results obtained from the questionnaires.	7
Central Greece	Regional development, rural development, research	Neutral to positive	region, comparison, indicator	Yes	Overall, text mining can be a useful tool as long as there are a lot sources and preferably in English language.	5
Vidzeme (LV)	regional development, regional planning, investment, economic development, financial investment, regional statistics, development planning	Neutral to positive	Public transport, parking	No	At the current stage of development of the system especially in Latvian language and in the given task of policy evaluation it does not create additional added value or new discoveries.	5
Central Bohemia (CZ)	Municipality, Economic Development		N.A.	No	The results of the text mining showed unvalid semantic combination of expressions which	3

Pilot	Most relevant topics	General tendency in observed sentiment	Topics with most negative sentiment	Supportive to the evaluation field work	Justification	Effort needed (in person days)
					are not usable in practice yet.	
Slovakia	Topics are only displayed in Slovak language	Neutral to positive	European Union, Future Trends	No	It was not possible to identify any additional information or resources relevant for the theme of the Evaluation report that could provide any additional value.	3
Mazowieckie (PL)	Text mining report missing					
Flanders (BE)	biodiversity, environment, agriculture and landscape	Neutral to positive	Environment, pollution, landscape and plant species	n.a.	n.a.	
Monaghan (IE)	County, local development, rural development, new community	Lightly positive	County, building service, information service, public services	Yes	Text Mining enabled a large amount of previous work and literature to be analysed to give a different perspective, with interesting insights and very useful sentiment quotes. Overall, the analysis confirms survey feedback.	

Table 7 Comparative overview of text-mining results

The synopsis of the results of the text mining shows on the one hand that due to the different selected policy measures only very few common topics could be identified. Terms used here include regional and rural development. On the other hand, no statements can be made for Finland and Slovakia on basis of the available reports, as the word lists are only available in the national language. It is also difficult to identify common patterns for terms with negative sentiment.

If we analyse general trends in the area of sentiment across the regions, we find that almost all the regions surveyed have a rating of "neutral to positive". This can presumably be explained

by the fact that the individual regions primarily used official documents for their curated reading lists. These are naturally kept in a neutral tone.

The pilot regions also indicated in their reports whether and why text-mining was meaningful and useful for their evaluation. Three pilots (Häme (FI), Slovakia, and Vidzeme (LV)) do not see any added value in using text-mining for their evaluation work. Four regions (Segóbriga, ES; Apulia, IT; Central Greece; Monaghan, IE), on the other hand, consider that this method has enriched and complemented their work. The time-wise effort to apply text mining in WP4 spans from one and a half to seven working days.

Those pilot regions that do not see any benefit from text mining have mainly stated that the application in the respective national language has caused difficulties, this also applies to the Greek region, which evaluates the tool positively in principle, but at the same time limits the usefulness preferably to analyses in English. It can be assumed that especially regions from large countries (i.e. Apulia (IT), Segóbriga (ES)) or from a large language area (i.e. Monaghan, IE) have advantages in Topic Modelling compared to small language communities (i.e. Vidzeme, LV; Häme, FI, Slovakia).

Another conclusion concerns the exact temporal use of text mining in an evaluation project. While within T4.5 text mining has been used in parallel to other methods of field research, it seems to make more sense to use topic modelling as input for interviews and/or workshops.

8 Factors supporting development in the pilot regions

Although the pilot regions differ in their characteristics, including their degree of urbanization and state of economic development, they all aim to increase the attractiveness of their region. Accordingly, each pilot had to indicate in its Evaluation Report key success factors and obstacles/barriers - factors that slowed down or made development more difficult and complex - in their region. These factors have been collected either by means of the survey or through interviews.

Pilot Region	Key Internal Success Factors
1. Flanders (BE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation degree • Ease of implementation • Ease of accessibility • Degree of compensation (funding)
2. Monaghan (IE)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political will, community uptake • Community buy in • LEADER Implementing Body • Clear Plans and Project Management • Promotion and training • Funding
3. Segóbriga (ES)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LEADER methodology • Proximity / Accessibility of LAG personnel • Funding • Thematic Working Groups • Support of regional authorities

Pilot Region	Key Internal Success Factors
4. Central Bohemia (CZ)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation with the capital city in policy setting • Operation of regional medical and social facilities • Innovative ICT technologies • Collaboration with academic sector • Gradual training of officials
5. Häme (FI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Leader funding • Agility: Applicants receive help easily and on a low threshold • Increasing visibility of Leader among potential applicants
6. Central Greece	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support of LEADER implementation bodies (LAGs) • Cooperation + communication among involved bodies • Efforts of regional authorities • Funding
7. Apulia (IT)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong context analysis supported by a bottom-up strategy • Clarity, concreteness and measurability of the objectives
8. Gevgelija-Strumica (NM)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease of application (methodology, expertise and helpful employees) • Preparation and good assessments • Involvement of all stakeholders
9. Mazowieckie (PL)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local specificity • Well-chosen selection criteria • Assistance from the employees of the office implementing the measure
10. Slovakia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>(Main obstacle: poor information on EU policy in Slovakia)</i>
11. Vidzeme (LV)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation between municipalities and entrepreneurs • Rural people's Positive mindset and willingness to cooperate • Support of LAGs • Funding / financial support • Wide range of areas can be supported

Table 6 Key internal Success factors

The success factors indicate various characteristics, features and/or preconditions that are important for achieving the desired goal(s). Although the specifics of the pilots differ in each region, there are a number of commonalities in the key success factors. The number and specificity of key success factors indicated differ from region to region, and partly also relate to how positive the evaluation results are.

When assessing key success factors and obstacles/barriers, it is useful to differentiate between *factors that closely relate to the policy measures themselves* (what one might term as 'internal' factors), as reported in table 6, and *external factors* relating to the economic, social, demographic, environmental/spatial, and political/policy context in which the policy measures are applied. Moreover, factors may also be double-sided, having a beneficial, success-like impact but in other ways may also act as a barrier, causing delays or decreases in beneficiaries or take-up at the same time. The impact of COVID-19 is a clear case in point.

Key 'internal' success factors

When it comes to 'internal' key success factors good community engagement and being able to mobilize parties, cooperation and political will, accessibility and support of staff in acquiring and implementing support, but also 'policy-intrinsic' factors such as the LEADER methodology,

the availability of funding as well as appropriate and targeted information and dissemination are most mentioned.

Community engagement and mobilizing parties works in two ways, as several policy measures and LEADER programmes can also be viewed as a vehicle for **community buy-in**, as in, e.g., the case of Monaghan (IE). Without community buy-in and visibility of the programme within the region, it is harder to achieve success. Yet community engagement requires community will and capacity at local level. Investment in training and capacity building are ways to stimulate community engagement. This may overcome community resistance to change. Community engagement also requires something else as the Monaghan case shows: “Citizens need to feel they are part of the solution rather than there being a top-down approach”.

Another closely linked success factor is the support by **local and regional authorities**, including regional development agencies, which play an important role in supporting regional development. In Segobriga (ES) for example, this holds for the support of the Provincial Rural Network in which the stakeholders linked to rural development in the province of Cuenca exchange ideas and experiences in the management and application of rural development policies.

The case of North Macedonia shows that procedural and institutional capacity can limit take-up and impact effective implementation. Responsible municipalities state that eligibility requirements are often too restrictive and do not adequately fit the needs of the rural population and the rural economy. But it also points at a “poor description of the application procedures by AFSARD, the institution that is directly involved in the execution of the measures, and (...) a large number of delays in deadlines in the process of executing the measure”.

Alignment with local and regional policy and close collaboration with policymakers and politicians have been indicated as a factor increasing chances of success.

Accessibility and support of employees of LAG staff and other staff is another key success factor. Applicants could approach employees with questions and comments. This accessibility increases the number of applicants and the degree of successful applications.

Lack of and less than optimal dissemination of information on funding opportunities and support but also **lack of awareness** of available policy measures and opportunities known to the population of (potential) beneficiaries can limit the outreach and effectiveness of policy measures, as several regions report, including Slovakia, Häme (FI), Monaghan (IE) and Segobriga (ES). The Monaghan case signals a lack of an integrated, multi-agency approach, pointing at a low awareness of the benefits and available support amongst target groups, a low-level knowledge base in communities, fear of bureaucracy involved in accessing grants, and a need to support with applications. The smaller beneficiaries are the more pressing is the need for information, e.g. for micro-companies in the Häme (FI) case. The Finnish case also points at the need for **better communication and knowledge transfer between offices and advisors**.

Problems of bureaucracy were also noted, e.g. with the system used for applications for funding (Häme, FI), in applying for funds in general (Mazowieckie, PL) and access to funding (Apulia, IT), planning and implementation complexities (Apulia (IT), Monaghan (IE)) and complicated procedures involving a “huge amount of formalities”, sometimes “very stressful” (Mazowieckie, PL), “too many steps in the process, unwieldy application process” and “gatekeeper mentality” (Monaghan, IE) or in general, as in Slovakia (“excessive bureaucracy”). In the case of Apulia, due to bureaucracy one out of two applications for funding was faced with programming errors of the regional administrations, leading to a large number of judicial appeals. The risk, as the Apulia case clearly points out, is that important opportunities for both farmers and SMEs to invest may be missed. In Central Greece not only bureaucracy but also **lack of political stability** play a role and affect implementation having led to changes in laws (“a multiplicity of laws”) and staff, hampering policy take-up and effective implementation. The case of Vidzeme (LV) seems an exception with “good project financial support and friendly creation of proposal”, “digital application forms” and a “transparent working model”. However, in the Latvian case the simultaneous announcement of several support programmes apart from rural development and LEADER, has had a significant upward impact on price increases, service quality and caused delays because of competition combined with a lack of capacity.

The **LEADER methodology** has been indicated as a key success factor in several pilot regions. This methodology entails a wide range of topics supported, ease of contact and support by LEADER implementing bodies and community groups and a broad capacity to respond to the needs of the territory. For example, in Häme (FI) applicants receive help easily and on a low threshold, describing LEADER as an agile actor. Likewise, in Segobriga (ES) proximity between the beneficiary and LEADER staff is a key factor, providing them a guarantee of success in developing their project. This relationship involves monitoring and tutoring individuals or entities that propose initiatives. More specifically, within the Local Action Group (LAG) structure there is a working group in charge of reflecting, searching and proposing ideas in relation to the theme or topic at hand. These thematic working groups are a success factor in the development of the strategy since they are a forum for specific strategic analysis that serves as a source and catalyst of ideas for the progress of the territory.

Also, the level of support offered in LEADER as against other forms of public support appears to play a role. In Segobriga (ES) beneficiaries indicate to have chosen LEADER because it meant a bigger grant, with a higher financial endowment, or simply because they are unaware of other types of aid. LEADER as a programme has also become more known over time which appears to have increased the number of applications and the reach of the measure. A core principle of the LEADER approach is cooperation, one of the claimed success factors behind reaching effective and long-term sustainable results in Vidzeme (LV).

Funding is another important success factor. Adequate funding is critical for achieving the envisioned goals whereas a lack of funding in some rural regions is seen as a hinderance to development. Projects that receive an appropriate amount of funding have a higher potential

for significant job creation and regional development. However, in several regions funding “needs further development” as one of the pilots put it, both in terms of level/degree of support to individual beneficiaries and in terms of availability at large, avoiding also fragmentation. More is by most seen as better. In Segobriga (ES) the greatest difficulties beneficiaries faced when starting the projects are financial difficulties, followed by the administrative processing of subsidies. In the case of Vidzeme (LV) on the other extreme, support rate are seen as high (up to 70%) and public funding sufficiently available.

From a programming perspective, a **strong context analysis supported by a bottom-up strategy** going hand in hand with **a clear strategic plan and clear objectives** contributes to its subsequent success, as the case of Apulia (IT), Vidzeme (LV), and Monaghan (IE) explicitly point out.

‘External’ key success factors

When it comes to **external factors** that stimulate or hinder development in the regions, mostly mentioned are the COVID-19 crisis and the economic downturn, demographic factors and the availability of resources in the region.

COVID-19, mentioned by several pilots, obviously belongs to the set of external factors. One would categorize COVID-19 as a factor that made - and continues to make - development more difficult and complex, mixing up plans and causing delays in implementation. This is especially the case for start-ups (Mazowieckie, PL), e.g. with COVID-19 having led to inhibited demand from business for innovative services in many industries. COVID-19 had some, but usually a limited impact on the functioning of the projects implemented under the measure in question. In Segobriga (ES), e.g., it slowed down investors' entrepreneurship plans, and COVID-19 coincided with the moment when LEADER grants would reach their forecasts in terms of mobilisation of private capital and generation of new businesses in the territory. Local administrations appear to have filled the gap by proposing projects in the same thematic policy domains.

Its impact also may in some cases be opposite including local entrepreneurship successes, e.g. benefiting from an increase in population due to remote work possibilities and multi-place residents (e.g. Häme, FI).

A **recession or economic downturn**, caused by COVID-19 or more in general, clearly affects the way and pace in which policy measures are implemented and find their way to potential beneficiaries. Economics may also impact beneficiaries' absorptive capacity for measures, and may reduce required investments and jobs, as the case of Vidzeme (LV) shows. A relative rise in economic activity as in Vidzeme (LV) (also very positively affecting the number of project applications), or in income and purchasing power across society as seen in Mazowieckie (PL), on the other hand may work out positively. In Greece the crisis delayed funding procedures and led to a reduction of the budget, resulting in a decreased number of beneficiaries. This was

further aggravated by difficulties in bank financing. In Latvia unpredictable and often changing national tax policy posed a serious obstacle to development and project implementation.

Economics also manifest themselves in other ways, such as **labour market rigidities** - as e.g. in Häme (FI) - which do not encourage companies to hire people. More in general, the stock of knowledge and skills of the local working population and of individual citizens, including their digital skills and the ability to use digital systems such as deployed by Leader (e.g. in Häme, FI), appears increasingly important.

In the case of Central Greece **weather phenomena** were also mentioned as major barrier, in particular where municipalities and road network projects were concerned.

Demography also is a crucial factor. Not only does business activity in rural areas crucially depend on the presence of a working population of sufficient clout. But demography also affects the presence of crucial infrastructure and public services like schools which in turn may have an effect on business (re)location choices. In the case of Häme (FI), company owners often appear to be parents of young families. This makes their location choices co-dependent of the availability of basic and other education for their children. Other external factors like **municipal policies and legislation affecting the ease of doing business** also affect the way policy measures prove to be effective and taken up. This especially holds for measures that involve business creation and diversification.

In low densely populated rural areas lack of human resources may play a role, such as in Vidzeme (LV) and in Monaghan (IE) with “lack of feet on the ground, raising the finances and push back from rural dwellers, reluctance to change”. Segobriga (ES) mentions “a lack of critical mass of population in the territory with the capacity and willingness to invest in new businesses”. In the Latvian case scarcity of access to land, adequate space for development of entrepreneurship and liveable (good quality) housing also acted as barriers to further development. The physical environment itself is increasingly under threat, even in the real rural areas, with loss of biodiversity being an important issue as the Irish case also shows. In the more developed, densely populated areas of north-western Europe, such as in Flanders (BE) **urbanisation** increasingly defines the context for rural land use. Limited possibilities of further expansion and pressure imposed by other functions or other residents cause rising land prices. Increased environmental concerns and a strict permit policy result in pressure on agriculture in the city outskirts, with land scarcity causes a strong competition between active farmers and other land users. They set, among others, the scene for increased use and emphasis on agri-environment-climate measures and management agreements.

9 Conclusions and recommendations

The evaluated policy measures are different in terms of local context in which they are to be implemented, theme, coverage and implementation status. This section outlines the general conclusions of the evaluation of the policy measures, in accordance to the results obtained from

the evaluation process in each region. Additionally, some recommendations are provided for the evaluation and design of future actions.

9.1 General Conclusions

1. The policy measures evaluated, involved the main stakeholders of the regions to tackle their policy challenges, and to promote an **integrated and participative approach** in their regions. This fact has been mentioned in all the pilots, although in some cases, the participation of farmers and SMEs has been lower (e.g.: Apulia, IT; Central Bohemian, CZ; Central Greece; Galilee, IL; Slovakia; Gevgelija-Strumica, MK)
2. There are seven policy measures evaluated that are being implemented through the LEADER program (IT, ES, GR, IR, FI, PL, LV).
 - The LEADER policy instrument was mainly delivered through **local projects and grants**, in collaboration with public-private partnerships. The projects should be a concrete and useful instrument that provide an answer to the policy challenge addressed, but in the evaluation reports, there is no clear references to the outputs of the projects. Most of them have included as outputs the supported projects themselves.
 - Most of the LEADER measures evaluated, designed their local or regional strategies with a focus on a **bottom-up approach** and clear objectives. However, the SME and farms, in some cases are the most dissatisfied with the effectiveness, the reasons are related in some cases with the implementation of the measure. There is a general feeling in some regions that the bureaucracy is overly complex for the applicants of the LEADER program, so a good organization and coordination with those responsible, would be essential to streamline the process and give support to the applicants. Also, in rural areas, farmers, companies, and communities are being particularly affected by the Corona pandemic, which has led to delays in the implementation of the measures evaluated.
3. All the measures evaluated, define their **objectives to add value in the pillars considered key** to make their territories more attractive. Most of them have evaluated policy measures with the aim of facilitating the creation of business opportunities, job creation, better living conditions, conserving and managing natural resources, or guaranteeing the quality of life and services to its inhabitants, among others (see Table 10, Annex 3). The impact of the policy measures evaluated, has been in most cases limited, and it should increase in the future. These are long-term goals that require strong top-down leadership and clear directionality, backed by a bottom-up strategy, in order to better achieve the set goals.
4. Policy measures present **their objectives clearly**, and some of them show a clear breakdown of planned activities / actions / projects which will be developed and delivered to help their regions meet these objectives and achieve the results. However, the implementation phase has not reached the expected results in participation (e.g. Segóbrina, ES; Apulia, IT; Monaghan, IE; Vidzeme, LV).
5. All regions have **communication and dissemination** mechanisms in place to communicate their objectives and achievements, although some fail to involve civil society, and potential

beneficiaries in a proactive way. Demography is sometimes a crucial factor (e.g. Segóbrina/Spain, Apulia/Italy, Häme/Finland); if there are few residents in the rural area, there are no or few business, and yet, all regions see the need to enhance the training and awareness of the rural population to address the new challenges and to involve them in a more proactive way. Business advisers could do more marketing for the measures if they had the appropriate resources; entrepreneurship coaching e.g. customer needs mapping, creating a local ecosystem, creating business networks, locally and together.

6. It is also observed that the regions do not **monitor or evaluate** their progress in a holistic way. All regions have identified the coherence of their measures with others at different levels (regional, national etc.). It would be desirable to ensure and monitor the results and milestones of the policy measures that add value (directly or indirectly) to the achievement of the common objective. These tools would facilitate midterm evaluations for decision making. At this time, it has only been possible to provide a general vision of the outputs of the measures. To meaningfully measure complex, policy challenges, we must do the work to define success simply, specifically, and starting with the outcomes of the policy measures.
7. In relation to the coherence, all regions have identified the **coherence of their measures** with other policies at regional or national levels. To do this, a safe space should be created for stakeholders to think outside of the box and come to an agreement about the actions to be implemented. In order to design a coherent and meaningful set of actions, it is then important to check if it answers the objectives and vision previously defined **and to make sure it is operational**. Some of the policy measures under the LEADER Program address the different dimensions of the problem, i.e. social, economic, and environmental dimensions, but do not clearly consider **the various territorial levels relevant to the solutions to be implemented**, for that reason, a more strategic and systematic coordination between regional and local governments is needed.
8. In most cases, the long-term goals of the regions, have been translated into applicable 4-5 year local development strategies. It is recommended to embed the drafting of an **Integrated Action Plan** within a period of 12 months of launching the project, that will address the policy challenge on a year-by-year basis.
9. And, last but not least, the uncertainty and economic recession associated with the COVID-19 pandemic has slowed down investors' entrepreneurship plans coinciding with the time when LEADER grants could be reaching their forecasts in terms of mobilizing private capital, and generating new businesses in the territory.

The policy measures evaluated have taken into account the main keys in their design, such as: involving the interest group in an active collaboration, creating a shared vision on how to address the problem, design objectives and actions, and allocate resources. That said, a few suggestions for clear improvement have been provided.

On the other hand, there seems to be more difficulties in the implementation phase. Here are some **good practices** in the pilot **implementation phase** that have been highly valued by the pilots.

1. **Training** has been a relevant factor for ideas and projects to emerge in **Monaghan (Ireland)**. People must first understand the savings potential of technology to carry out projects and identify opportunities for community-based environmental action. For example, 33 community groups in Monaghan are carrying out biodiversity plans for their area. This would not have happened without the initial investment in **training and capacity building**.
2. The degree of participation depends on **the ease of application**, the degree of compensation for the effort, the need for the measure in each region or environment and the type of farm. The number of agri-environment agreements (AEA) in **Flanders (Belgium)**, almost doubled by 8000 in just one year, but there is a clear change in the type of agreements. For farmers, some measures are relatively cheap and easy to apply, while the benefit to the local environment is substantial, from reducing environmental pollution to promoting local biodiversity. For the realisation of the measures in different rural areas, farm advisors have assumed an active role. Every province and community have a visible contact point for further information on technical implementation. The ease of accessibility has increased farmers' participation in the policy instrument of agri-environment-climate measures. The primary recommendation here is to ensure that **enough flexibility and entrepreneurship** is appropriately fostered and supported.
3. The need for **information on Leader opportunities** is continuous and requires many different channels. In the informational events of the **Greek** policy measure, a detailed summary was provided on the objectives and content of the Local Program, as well as a presentation of the process of evaluation, integration and monitoring of the implementation of the investment plans of the beneficiaries, as well as of interlocal cooperation plans. During the implementation of the three Calls for Expression of Interest, a total of 76 informative events were held in cities in the area of intervention of the Local Program.
4. The objective of **Latvia's policy measure** is to increase private investment in businesses, so **the cooperation of municipalities with local entrepreneurs** was essential in the planning and implementation process in order to accurately identify which public infrastructure is important to entrepreneurs, so that they are encouraged to make private investment in companies and create new jobs.

Most of the measures evaluated are still in the **implementation phase** and this is a crucial stage. This stage has to do with HOW to move forward with actions, which can be complicated, therefore it is important to review the challenges that implementation can present such as: making sure a strategy is operational, understanding the local conditions for implementation, review the commitment of the agents involved with the purpose of implementation, and monitor the follow-up of the progress made in the implementation.

9.2 Recommendations

9.2.1 Recommendations for local action

Provide training and capacity building in pilot regions with low and moderate socio-economic growth: Successful local action needs both absorptive capacity of local stakeholders and

learning by interaction. People must first understand the savings potential of technology to carry out projects and identify opportunities for community-based environmental action. This also refers to a need for fundamental **education and awareness on digital transformation**, and environmental, transition to a low-carbon economy, and climate resilient opportunities, which have become important needs. This requires people on the ground, who are prepared to support local communities, as well as collaboration with innovation and development centres with specific actions, i.e., biodiversity plans, digital plan, etc.

Establish at regional level proactive and improved communication on policy measures and funding opportunities: Several regions have reported that a lack of and less than optimal dissemination of information on funding opportunities and support but also lack of awareness of available policy measures and opportunities known to the population of (potential) beneficiaries could limit the outreach and effectiveness of policy measures. Albeit all 12 regions have in principle communication and dissemination mechanisms in place to communicate their objectives and achievements, some fail to involve civil society, and potential beneficiaries in a proactive way.

Lower the administrative burden for regional beneficiaries of funding schemes: Problems of bureaucracy were present in several regions, e.g. with the system used for applications for funding, in applying for funds in general and access to funding. Regional institutions thus should either lower the administrative burdens within funding schemes and/or offer support and coaching for administrating projects thin policy interventions that are not managed in the pilot regions.

Develop institutional capacity and institutional thickness to foster growth and compensate for political instability: Especially regions with low and moderate socio-economic growth should concentrate their development efforts in developing and expanding institutional capacity at regional level. Some regions have indicated political instability as a factor hampering the success of regional policy measures. Institutional thickness refers to the density of institutions that act in a territory to promote development actions. The main idea of this approach is that the greater is the institutional thickness of a region, the greater is its capacity for growth. Institutional thickness offers also a regional fabric to buffer and compensate for perturbations (e.g. unforeseen political changes) in the system.

Establish a strong bottom-up planning culture that involves all relevant regional stakeholders: As the comparative analysis of the drivers for successful policy implementation in the pilot regions has shown a strong context analysis supported by a bottom-up strategy going hand in hand with a clear strategic plan and clear objectives contributes to its subsequent success from a programming perspective. Pilot regions should continue their efforts to involve regional stakeholders in strategy development and also implementation.

Make further use of the LEADER methodology to unleash regional transformation in the pilot regions: This methodology entails a wide range of topics supported, ease of contact and support by LEADER implementing bodies and community groups and a broad capacity to

respond to the needs of the territory. More specifically, within the Local Action Group (LAG) structure there is a working group in charge of reflecting, searching and proposing ideas in relation to the theme or topic at hand. These thematic working groups are a success factor in the development of the strategy since they are a forum for specific strategic analysis that serves as a source and catalyst of ideas for the progress of the territory. The LEADER methodology can also inform regional stakeholders on evaluation work, as the evaluation of regional policy measures is still poorly established in most regions and the LEADER PROGRAM has developed guidelines and tools for conducting LEADER / CLLD assessment activities at the local level.

Ensure better strategic and systematic coordination between regional and local governments:

As some of the Pilot Evaluation Reports show, policy measures under the LEADER Program address the different dimensions of the problem, i.e. social, economic, and environmental dimensions, but do not clearly consider the various territorial levels relevant to the solutions to be implemented. Thus regional policy makers are advised to better address these multilevel governance issues already in the stage of programme design.

9.2.2 Recommendations for future evaluation studies in the pilot regions

Establish and improve a proper programme monitoring: Up to date the pilot regions do not monitor or evaluate their progress in a holistic way. For the future regions should aim ensuring and monitoring the results and milestones of the policy measures that add value (directly or indirectly) to the achievement of the set common objective. These tools would facilitate midterm evaluations for policy learning and corresponding decision making. For the time being, it has only been possible to provide a general vision of the outputs of the measures in the pilot regions. To meaningfully measure complex, policy challenges, logic modelling or logic framework analysis should become a common practice to be able in the future to define success simply, specifically, and starting with the outcomes and/or impacts of the policy measures.

Evaluate the complete policy mix in support of rural regions: If rural areas are to become attractive locations again, this requires the coordinated use of a **comprehensive policy mix across** different policy domains. This necessarily leads to new challenges in evaluation. In the future, it will be necessary to evaluate not only individual programs (e.g. CAP, ERDF, etc.) but also the implementation and impact of the entire policy mix in a region. Such an analysis could also hint to existing policy inconsistencies that may hamper successful development.

System evaluation for rural areas: In addition to policy mix, **the interaction of the different institutions and actors** in a region is also an essential influencing factor for the development of the region. While the evaluation of innovation systems is already a common practice, such evaluations for rural areas are still the exception. Such studies could help to identify moments of system failure and suggest appropriate policy intervention.

9.3 Linkages between policy evaluation work and the next steps of Foresight exercises in pilot regions

The evaluation work in T.4.5 is part of the Foresight initiative work that the pilots carry out in their own regions. After the evaluation work pilots have clarified and consolidated links between the evaluation work and the practical work done in regional FS exercises. The pilots gathered for a joint workshop to present the evaluation results and their linkages to each ongoing regional foresight initiative. In this workshop pilots presented their lessons learned in policy evaluation in relation to concept of rural attractiveness and the content of action plan that will be produced in every FS initiative. The focus was on concept of rural attractiveness in previous policies for regional growth and development and if and how this is addressed in each pilot's own visioning process towards the final vision of each region's future; how the region will look like, who it will attract and why.

Through the evaluation work pilots have viewed closely to policy measures in progress in each pilot area. This has allowed pilots to identify measures that have already been validated and also those that for one reason or another are not progressing or succeeding. These lessons are utilized in the future as part of the FS initiative work.

Evaluation Cluster Map

The diagram groups pilots according to common themes and priorities identifies in T4.5. A node linking two or more regions provides common ground for exploration of new policy measures, a task due to start in the coming months. Inter-pilot similarities help facilitate cross-border learning that regional foresight teams can leverage to see what worked, or didn't, in other places, and why, before developing an optimal intervention for their rural area.

<https://polirural.eu/pilots/polirural-evaluation-based-cluster-map/>

10 Annex 1: Regional indicators used in the cluster analysis

Code	Description	Year
popdens	population density (inh./km ²)	Eurostat 2018
pop014	percentage of the population aged less than 15 years	Eurostat 2019
pop1564	percentage of population between 15 and 64 years	Eurostat 2020
pop65	percentage of the population aged more than 65	Eurostat 2021
gdppps	GDP/head (PPS), EU25=100	Eurostat 2018
empagr	agriculture employment (% of total)	Eurostat 2018
empserv	industry employment (% of total)	Eurostat 2018
empind	services employment (% of total)	Eurostat 2018
gvar	GVA-Regional gross value added	Eurostat 2017
emptot	total employment rate (ages 15-64 as % of pop. ages 15-64)	Eurostat 2018
empf	female employment rate (ages 15-64 as % of pop. Ages 15-64)	Eurostat 2019
empm	male employment rate (ages 15-64 as % of pop. ages15-64)	Eurostat 2021
unemptot	total unemployment rate (%)	Eurostat 2023
unemplt	long term unemployed(% of total unempl.)	Eurostat 2024
gdph	GDP/hours worked (EU28=100)	Eurostat 2015
pre-prim	percentage of active population with pre-primary educatin	Eurostat 2023
tert	percentage of active population with tertiary education	Eurostat 2023
knowint	Employment in technology and knowledge-intensive sectors	2018
knowwo	Knowledge workers	Eurostat 2023
roadacc	Share of population in a 120 km radius accessible by road within 1h30	DG Regio (2016)

Code	Description	Year
railacc	Share of population in a 120 km radius accessible by rail within 1h30	DG Regio (2014)
broadband	% of total households with access to broadband	Eurostat ICT survey 2018
internet	% of total households with internet access.	Eurostat ICT survey 2018

Table 8 Regional Indicators considered in the Cluster Analysis

Descriptive Statistics of the Regional Indicators

	Min	Max	Mean	St, Dev,	Skew	Kurtosis
popdens	25,7	508,8	120,8	42426,5	5,7	39,6
pop014	0,1	0,4	0,2	2,5	-0,4	-0,1
pop1564	0,2	1,7	0,8	2,7	-1,9	12,6
pop65	0,1	0,6	0,2	3,1	0,7	2,4
gdppps	58,9	108,7	75,0	35,0	1,4	6,5
empagr	0,1	39,4	6,5	7,5	2,4	5,7
empserv	41,0	88,5	65,2	9,7	-0,1	-0,4
empind	11,4	46,3	28,3	7,4	0,0	-0,3
emptot	40,1	78,6	63,4	8,2	-0,5	-0,1
empf	24,0	76,1	55,4	10,3	-0,6	0,2
empm	46,6	85,6	71,2	7,7	-0,8	0,3
unemptot	4,0	24,8	9,0	5,7	1,4	1,4
unemplt	4,1	80,4	38,5	15,8	0,2	-0,8
unempf	2,3	33,3	10,0	6,8	1,2	0,9
unempy	4,2	58,4	18,9	12,0	1,3	1,1

	Min	Max	Mean	St, Dev,	Skew	Kurtosis
roadacc	50,0	101,5	70,5	50,0	101,5	70,5
railacc	0,2	11,2	3,7	0,2	11,2	3,7
broadband	70,0	91,0	80,8	70,0	91,0	80,8
popdens	25,7	508,8	120,8	42426,5	5,7	39,6
pop014	0,1	0,4	0,2	2,5	-0,4	-0,1
pop1564	0,2	1,7	0,8	2,7	-1,9	12,6
pop65	0,1	0,6	0,2	3,1	0,7	2,4

Table 9 Descriptive Statistics of the Regional Indicators

11 Annex 2: Result of the fieldwork

The common PoliRural evaluation questions were regarding:

11.1 Effectiveness

To what extent has the policy measure achieved its initial objectives (i.e. as laid down at the start of the measure)?

Figure 6 To what extent has the policy measure achieved its initial objectives (i.e. as laid down at the start of the measure) in the pilots?

To what extent has the policy measure achieved its initial objectives (i.e. as laid down at the start of the measure)?

Figure 7 To what extent has the policy measure achieved its initial objectives (i.e. as laid down at the start of the measure) in the clusters?

Figure 8 To what extent did the external factors matter/contribute in achieving these objectives in the pilots?

Figure 9 To what extent did the external factors matter/contribute in achieving these objectives in the clusters?

11.2 Relevance

To what extent did the objectives of the policy measure meet the initial needs?

Figure 10 To what extent did the objectives of the policy measure meet the initial needs in the pilots?

To what extent did the objectives of the policy measure meet the initial needs?

Figure 11 To what extent did the objectives of the policy measure meet the initial needs in the clusters?

To what extent has the policy measure contributed to achieving the rural policy objectives/package for the region as a whole?

Figure 12 To what extent has the policy measure contributed to achieving the rural policy objectives/package for the region as a whole in the pilots?

To what extent has the policy measure contributed to achieving the rural policy objectives/package for the region as a whole?

Figure 13 To what extent has the policy measure contributed to achieving the rural policy objectives/package for the region as a whole in the clusters?

Figure 14 To what extent do the needs and objectives targeted by the policy measure still apply at the end of its implementation? In other words, is there reason/room for extending the policy measure in the pilots?

Figure 15 To what extent do the needs and objectives targeted by the policy measure still apply at the end of its implementation? In other words, is there reason/room for extending the policy measure in the clusters?

11.3 Coherence

Figure 16 To what extent the policy measure is internally coherent, i.e., in its objectives and actions in the pilots?

Figure 17 To what extent the policy measure is internally coherent, i.e., in its objectives and actions in the clusters?

Figure 18 To what extent the policy measure is coherent with other policy interventions with similar objectives in the pilots?

Figure 19 To what extent the policy measure is coherent with other policy interventions with similar objectives in the clusters?

To what extent is the policy measure part of an integral rural policy programme or package with a clear set of objectives?

Figure 20 To what extent is the policy measure part of an integral rural policy programme or package with a clear set of objectives in the pilots?

To what extent is the policy measure part of an integral rural policy programme or package with a clear set of objectives?

Figure 21 To what extent is the policy measure part of an integral rural policy programme or package with a clear set of objectives in the clusters?

Figure 22 To what extent does the policy measure link and add to other local, regional and national policy measures in the pilots?

Figure 23 To what extent does the policy measure link and add to other local, regional and national policy measures in the clusters?

To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other EU policy measures? CAP, LEADER, policies of other DGs (e.g., REGIO, CONNECT)

Figure 24 To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other EU policy measures? CAP, LEADER, policies of other DGs (e.g., REGIO, CONNECT) in the pilots?

To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other EU policy measures? CAP, LEADER, policies of other DGs (e.g., REGIO, CONNECT)

Figure 25 To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other EU policy measures? CAP, LEADER, policies of other DGs (e.g., REGIO, CONNECT) in the clusters?

12 Annex 3: Table of the objectives of the Political Measures evaluated by the Pilots

Pillar	Objectives	Policy Measures
1. Apulia (Italy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better living conditions and quality of life; • Support the creation of sources of employment in the region; • Improve the creation and implementation of local development programs with a focus on Business Economy and Innovation; • Support the creation and the diffusion of public-private partnership 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation and promotion of Local Development Strategies
2. Segóbriga (Spain)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job creation through support for SMEs in diversification activities of the rural economy, promoting training, innovation and the settlement of entrepreneurs in rural areas, and in the local agri-food industry. • Efficient use of rural resources and the maintenance, conservation and recovery of cultural, historical and architectural heritage, • Improve Improvement of public services and the quality of life in rural areas, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and implementation of a regional Country Plan
3. Central Bohemian (Czech Republic)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support wellbeing of all inhabitants, • Minimizing intra-regional disparities and • Support the local identity to sustain the proper development of all areas of the Region, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a regional development strategy
4. Gevgelija-Strumica (North Macedonia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments in infrastructure for development of agriculture, forestry and water economy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investments in infrastructure for development
5. Slovakia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The EU Quality Policy aiming at protecting the names of specific products to promote their unique characteristics, linked to their geographical origin as well as traditional know-how 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regulations to increase competitiveness by EU Quality Policy
6. Vidzeme (Latvia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Goal of M19.21 is to promote public involvement in initiatives to strengthen the local economy, • Objective of SO 3.3.1 is to increase the amount of private investment in the regions, while also ensuring economic activity and promoting employment (national level) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promote public involvement in local economic strengthening initiatives
7. Hame (Finland)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Encourage new small businesses to start up and, in the case of existing small businesses, to support diversification, expansion, services, productization, investment, communication, co-operation and internationalization in terms of locality, local services and entrepreneurship development. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Supporting new and growing business opportunities in farms and rural areas

Pillar	Objectives	Policy Measures
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Companies are also encouraged to develop new and innovative solutions to strengthen local services and local entrepreneurship and employment. Projects related to the employment of young people add value to the projects. 	
8. Central Greece (Greece)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotes the competitiveness of local companies and consequently entrepreneurship, in the field of processing / marketing of agricultural products Promotes actions for the diversification of the rural economy by creating multiple activities and additional income as well as measures to improve the quality of life in rural areas, through actions that utilize the rich natural resources of the intervention area as well as the provision and improving services to the rural population 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of capacities for employment and diversification in rural areas
9. Flanders (Belgium)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investment in innovation and education directed towards future farming and societal challenges and focus on increased resilience and sustainability of the agricultural sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial compensation for environmental / biodiversity measures
10. Monaghan (Ireland)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protection and Sustainable Use of Water Resources Protection and Improvement of Local Biodiversity Development of Renewable Energy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of Local Development Strategy - Environmental Theme
11. Poland	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stimulate the entrepreneurship of the inhabitants, Support the development of existing companies and the creation of new ones. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Supporting the creation of new companies and the development of the local labour market

Table 10 Objectives of the Political Measures evaluated by the Pilots

13 Annex 4: Overview on Conclusions and Recommendations by Pilots

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
1. Apulia (Italy)	<p>From the evaluation of measure 19 we can say that, in general, the various stakeholders consider it to be unsatisfactory. As widely said, this probably derives from the delay in its application in the Apulia region.</p> <p>In detail, we noted that the assessment of effectiveness, hence the progress of the measure towards achieving its objectives, looking for evidence of why, if or how these changes are attributed to the policy measure, has achieved more negative than positive results. The analysis of the two open questions was interesting, which highlighted the success factors and obstacles of the measure. In fact, it turned out that there is a strong context analysis supported by a bottom-up strategy accompanied by clarity of the objectives to be achieved. The obstacles, on the other hand, have highlighted the excessive bureaucracy borne by farmers and SMEs is great. The risk is that important opportunity to invest may be missed. To this problem, we must certainly add the current Covid-19 pandemic which has slowed down the implementation of the Apulia PSR and therefore of measure 19.</p> <p>As for the relevance, therefore the analysis of the relationship between needs and problems and the objectives of measure 19, the results were more negative than positive. Farmers and SMEs are the most dissatisfied.</p> <p>Coherence, therefore, how measure 19 is aligned with other local, regional, national or EU policy measures, was more negative than positive. Again, SMEs and farmers are the most dissatisfied.</p> <p>Specific questions on measure 19 found more negative opinions than positive opinions. Again, the negative aspects are borne by SMEs and farmers. The difference between the blocking of general questions and the blocking of specific questions is the presence of abstentions. In fact, for each question, at least 2 are those who prefer not to answer or are not interested.</p> <p>This analysis allowed us to analyse and grasp the vision of the various stakeholders regarding measure 19. Thanks to it, in fact, we were able to ascertain that in general there is a contrasting vision of measure 19. Farmers and SMEs are certainly the most dissatisfied in fact they often gave negative answers. On the contrary, local PAs and the agronomist are on average satisfied with the work done so far. The dissatisfaction of farmers and SMEs is certainly consistent with the delay in the application of measure 19.</p> <p>For the future, it is good to remember the problems that have emerged. One above all is certainly the bureaucracy. The same, besides being expensive, means that the measures of the RDP (therefore of measure 19) go slowly with ease of error. It is no coincidence that, from what was approved, it was subjected overall to 834 judicial appeals, both extraordinary and hierarchical, which significantly affect the progress of administrative, physical, and financial progress. The emergency of Covid-19 also taught us that the unexpected is just around the corner, so good organization and coordination with the various stakeholders is essential.</p>
2. Segóbriga (Spain)	<p>The LEADER measure is the most important rural development strategy implemented in the territory, not only in financial terms but also due to the mobilization and involvement of the population that it achieves. The LAG ADESIMAN budget was reduced by 30% compared to the 2007-2013 period.</p> <p>It is necessary to give continuity to LEADER in the new period 2021-27, to remain a strong and solid measure, to continue helping and offering opportunities to people who wish to develop their professional activity in rural areas, in the post-Covid era.</p> <p>The launch of sub-measure 19.2 LEADER, promoted by the ADESIMAN GAL, encountered several difficulties:</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Routine work breakdown and a very slow restart due to the change in procedures in the transition between 2007-2013 and 2014-2020. • Non-availability of the payment and management computer application until mid-2018. <p>It is essential to give as much continuity as possible to the procedures during the transition period and to speed up possible changes as much as possible. It is necessary to make payment and management tool available well in advance, so they do not represent a brake on the correct implementation of projects.</p> <p>Most of the executed projects come from local administrations, followed by SMEs and to a lesser extent individuals, specifically men. The lack of individualized promoters responds to a lack of critical mass of population with the capacity and will to invest in new businesses. Local administrations have filled this gap by proposing projects that have largely been related to the efficient use of energy resources and public infrastructures.</p> <p>Next period it is necessary to focus on stopping the depopulation in order to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain the human and material investment capacity in new businesses that generate employment and wealth. • Promote the projects that arise from the private initiative. <p>The uncertainty and economic recession associated with the COVID-19 pandemic has slowed down investors' entrepreneurship plans, coinciding with the time when LEADER grants could be reaching their forecasts in terms of mobilizing private capital and generating new businesses in the territory. It is necessary to disseminate and try to get the best possible performance from the new instruments such as the Recovery Funds, the new CAP, etc.</p> <p>Measure 19.2 is boosting the participation and involvement in the decision-making process on the development of their area. Measure 19.2 has played a discreet role to integrate or to improve the conditions of Vulnerable population in the territory (30% of those surveyed affirm that it has favored these groups). Regarding the promotion of equality, 37.3% of responses affirm that measure 19.2 has contributed in a great-moderate extent to the promotion of equality in the territory.</p> <p>It is necessary to reinforce disseminating LEADER activities to maximize its effects among rural population, being able to collect ideas and meet the needs of the different groups present in the territory.</p> <p>Most of the projects (67%) are related to the creation of Public Infrastructures and Services to reduce the Carbon Footprint. 15% are related to SME, Diversification and Employment. The rest of the projects are distributed equally between the promotion of Agrifood companies and the tourism sector with 9% of the projects for each of these objectives.</p> <p>The positive contribution in these objectives reinforces the need for continuity of LEADER since these are aspects included in the future vision of the development of the territory.</p> <p>In the opinion of the beneficiaries, the greatest difficulties they have faced when starting the projects have been financial difficulties (36%) and to a lesser extent difficulties with the administrative processing of the subsidy. On the contrary, the close treatment and support received by the GAL technicians has been an advantage and added value when it comes to improving the effectiveness of the measure.</p> <p>It is essential to reinforce LEADER's financial endowment for the future so that the LAG can maintain its work of stimulating and supervising new projects and business initiatives.</p> <p>Regarding effectiveness, the LAG affirms that the forecasts regarding the execution of outputs of non-productive projects will be achieved. In the contrary, it does not seem the same for the productive projects since the objectives will not be achieved due to the aforementioned recession</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>and economic uncertainty associated with COVID-19. Regarding the results, the number of jobs created is below forecasts, taking into account the economic difficulties that exist in the territory as well as the demographic crisis already mentioned.</p> <p>It is key for the LAG to continue promoting projects associated with the circular economy, the implementation of community composting, investment in efficient public lighting, etc., so that they serve as a lever for other productive initiatives and to arise awareness about the principles of Smart Villages.</p> <p>Regarding Relevance, the objectives set out in sub-measure 19.2 are balanced since each of them meets a similar number of needs. At the same time, it is observed that all the Objectives of measure 19.2 have connections with “current” needs, so it can be said that these objectives remain in force.</p> <p>Beyond measure 19.2, it is also necessary to boost Cooperation between Local Action Groups in order to continue advancing in projects that seek harmonized solutions to common problems such as differentiated taxation for rural areas.</p> <p>Regarding Coherence, sub-measure 19.2 is harmonized with a large number of local, regional and national Plans related to depopulation, conservation and improvement of the environment and business promotion and entrepreneurship.</p> <p>It is essential that in the new period LEADER continues in promoting the European principles of circular economy, resource efficiency and sustainable development.</p>
3. Central Bohemian (Czech Republic)	<p>The most valuable finding of the evaluation process is the fact that the Development strategy of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2019-2024, up to 2030 is still acceptable, valid and fully usable to deal with identified needs even under the current conditions affected by the covid-19 pandemic. Due to identified obstacles, the Action Plan should be communicated to all relevant stakeholders, measures should be discussed and explained internally with relevant Departments of the Regional Authority of the Central Bohemian Region and also with all regional partners to ensure acceptability of suggested measures. Particular measures should be tailor-made according to specific needs of areas of the Region with respect to the characteristics of these areas (rural vs. metropolitan) and contribute to minimizing intra-regional disparities. The Action Plan should promote the use of innovative tools and approaches, include and strengthen collaboration with the academic sector taking into account the existing research infrastructure.</p> <p>As mentioned earlier, the Development strategy of the territorial district of the Central Bohemian Region, for the period 2019-2024, up to 2030 - as a mid- to long-term strategy - is fully valid, it is aligned with the Innovation Strategy of the Czech Republic 2019 - 2030 and the Regional Development Strategy 2021+ as core policies related to (sustainable) regional development on the national level. Although the Strategy was adopted at the end of 2019, it is fully usable on the level of the (covid-19) recovery strategy for the whole Region and it is applicable to the strengthening of resilience of the territory.</p> <p>Considering impacts of the covid-19 pandemic, major issues related to the implementation of proposed policy measures are related with financing, because investment funds are redirected to activities related to dealing with the pandemic and financing of regional programs is cut due to the decline in GDP and tax revenue.</p> <p>In terms of funding, the Regional Permanent Conference as a communication, planning and coordination platform has a potential via using the comprehensive policy document - the Action Plan - to define a common understanding of the needs and determine the direction of ESIF and national resources into specific areas of the Central Bohemian Region. The Conference is (was) involved in the preparation stage of the programming period 2021-2027, including the</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>preparation of the Regional Development Strategy 2021+ of the Czech Republic. Through these activities, it is possible to influence the targeting of the new generation of operational programmes and to supervise whether their implementation contributes to the regional priorities and specific objectives of the Central Bohemian Region set out in the Strategy, including defined needs related to quality of life and wellbeing.</p>
4. Gevgelija-Strumica (North Macedonia)	<p>According to the results of the conducted survey supporting the policy evaluation process in North Macedonia, policy measure 124 - Investments in infrastructure for development of agriculture, forestry and water economy, is to a great extent effective, relevant and coherent.</p> <p>In relation to the effectiveness of measure 124 in North Macedonia, it can be concluded that in most of the municipalities as main beneficiaries, this measure has achieved its main objective. Three groups of factors were determined as key obstacles in the process of implementation of this measure: financial, institutional capacity, political and procedural factors. From these groups of factors institutional capacity is the dominant constraining factor. These results are consistent with large number of expert observations where one of the main sources for the current situation of the institutional capacity is the significant influence of politics in the employment process. Continuous usage of the public administration as bias electoral body by the political parties in the last three decades has resulted significant deterioration of the technical capacities in the municipalities and the central government.</p> <p>Based on the survey, it can be concluded that measure 124 is perceived as consistent with the infrastructural needs of the municipalities but it is not contributing enough in resolving the infrastructural problems in rural areas. Even though the measure has positive impact, the amount of allocated financial support combined with the limited financial capacities of the municipalities does not allow delivering of projects that can make a change in the context of rural attractiveness. As a specific limitation emphasized by large size of municipalities is that the measures cannot significantly support the infrastructure that enables access to agricultural arable lands.</p> <p>According to the responding municipalities, measure 124 is coherent with the policy objectives and other programs for rural development on national, regional and local level, and it is designed in accordance to the EU requirements in the pre-accession process, as well as the EU CAP.</p> <p>According to the survey results and responses from municipalities, the measure 124 is relevant and necessary and it should be continued in the future. Considering all above-mentioned conclusions, the following recommendations for improving the measure 124 are provided:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding frequent changes in the initially defined deadlines for budget transfers which will allow consistent flow of finance in the municipalities thus avoidance of execution of the stages of the infrastructural projects. Secured and consistent inflow of finance enables on time payment of the financial obligations towards the commercial entities involved in the project execution and better negotiation power for the municipalities resulting in better prices for products and services. • More frequent involvement of the relevant stakeholders (direct and indirect) in the process of designing the measures in order to achieve even more accurate consistency of the measure with the real infrastructural needs. By improving the approach in this direction, policy makers will become more aware about the specific need for roads that will enable better access to agricultural arable lands. • Structural changes that will allow lower impact of the politics in the approval process. • Achieving higher level of consistency in the process of publishing calls which will allow municipalities to create better plans in accordance to the potential sources of financing. This improvement in the process will also enable municipalities to better manage their own financial capacities and to look for additional sources for financing. • Core recommendation in the context of improving measure 124 is a proposal for creating a structural program for increasing the capacities of the public administration on how to access publicly available funds, international funds and EU funds. This program should also

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>include increasing the technical capacity in the area of project execution, project monitoring and project reporting. By developing and execution of this type of program will allow better access to external funds, increasing the municipality budget for co-financing and higher level of compliance with the specific rules of using funds from the National rural development program.</p>
5. Slovakia	<p>Overall the implementation of the EU Quality Policy in Slovakia was designed and implemented appropriately and coherently since its introduction in 2003. The national legal framework allowing the implementation of the EU Quality Policy in Slovakia is appropriate and in line with the EU legislation. In this regard, additional attention needs to be given to other voluntary labels being used on the national level especially in terms of informing the consumers on differences between them. This would be highly beneficial for improving the EU Quality Policy implementation in Slovakia.</p> <p>Some positive results have been achieved over the last 17 years, but there is still a lot of space for improvement of the EU Quality Policy implementation in Slovakia and increasing its effectiveness. This measure requires more attention from the responsible Ministry, relevant associations, retailers and consumers. Therefore, the decision needs to be taken at the national level if more effort and resources shall be put into this measure or not, depending on the available capacities of the relevant public authorities and interest of group of producers.</p> <p>The main issue that came out of the evaluation process is very poor information on EU Quality Policy implementation process in Slovakia. At the moment there is just website run by the MofA&RD of SR. Furthermore, there is not much motivation for producers to have an interest in the registration process. Therefore, priority should be given to overcoming this.</p> <p>Recommendation No 1: Increased effort in the area of promoting the EU Quality Policy is needed in Slovakia. This requires more proactive attitude of the responsible MofAR of the Slovak republic by kick starting the drafting process of a National Marketing Strategy prepared in broad consultation process with relevant stakeholders and actors. This could be one of the tools to start the public discussion on this issue and also positively contribute to rising awareness on EU Quality Policy in Slovakia. This strategy can address important issues already identified by stakeholders, such as very strict national legislation for the implementation of the EU legislation, and find many others that need to be addressed. The national legislation should reflect the specific interests and requirements of local entrepreneurs and set very simple and clear rules, avoiding to much complicating their life, but instead find the ways how to make it as simple as possible and less demanding. Local conditions and needs need to be reflected when adapting the European legislation to the Slovak perspective and thus avoid any harm or hardship for domestic producers. It should include regular information campaigns on the explaining the EU Quality Policy and difference from other similar policies, organizing regular events focused on the presentation of the aims of the EU Quality Policy and contribution it can have to protecting, safeguarding and promoting the production of local domestic products not only on national, but also on European and global levels. Successful implementation of the marketing strategy requires allocation of adequate financial resources to support it. The financial contribution should be continuous and not a single case or option. This could be one of the factors positively influencing the interest and motivation of producers to get involved and start the registration process.</p> <p>Recommendation No 2: There is a need to support and help producers to market their protected products better. In order to better promote the products already holding the registration requires involvement of all actors, at all production levels from farm to table. The useful tool could be common crafting of the National Plan for promotion of the products holding the registrations. The registered products should be used also officially by public institutions and authorities as part of national honour and pride. This could generate more interest from producers and their organizations to apply for the various registrations.</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>Recommendation No 3: Protected products require a specific recognition and work with consumers to inform them that these are the quality products that they can trust and learn to distinguish them from others. Special promotion campaigns dedicated to PDOs, PGIs and TSGs are necessary to be introduced. They can be prepared and implemented in joint collaboration of the Ministry and associations involved. Promotion campaigns should include information on the quality of raw material and ingredients used for the production of registered foodstuffs to distinguish them from the others and the prices the consumers will have to pay for them, which are usually higher than other similar products. Positive impact on human health and environment should be highlighted. Closer the food products are produced to consumer the lower is the impact on the environment, since transportation and handling is limited. Slovak consumers need to be better inform to make the right shopping choices and establish regular shopping habits. The EU Quality Policy crates a legal framework for support and protection of original and traditional food products of quality and at the same time safeguarding traditions and culture of the given region. It can also have a positive effect on stimulating the local and regional agricultural and food production. These products are more attractive and interesting for consumers and provide a higher guarantee of food safety since they are more in depth controlled by authorized public control authorities. This creates an additional value of these agricultural and food products.</p> <p>Recommendation No 4: Special focus needs to be dedicated to the PDOs since there are only 2 at the moment holding the registration, which is quite low in comparison with neighbouring and other EU countries. Both of them were register some time ago. First one in 2014 and the second one in 2017. PDOs contribute the most to local production since there is a close production cycle in a certain territory.</p> <p>Recommendation No 5: Establish a communication and regular contact with other EU countries in order to exchange experiences, views and obstacles hindering the implementation of the EU Quality Policy and finding jointly ways how to overcome them.</p> <p>Recommendation No 6: Establish a regular channel of communication with all relevant stakeholders and actors via a specific platform or network, which is open, active and effective.</p> <p>Recommendation No 7: Explore the possible ways of reducing the time needed for obtaining the registration since the current span of 2 – 3 years, sometimes even 4 years, which might significantly contribute to decreasing the attractiveness of the EU Quality Policy for producers and their associations.</p> <p>Recommendation No 8: Generally, higher support of domestic food producers from the public authorities is highly encouraged. It should move from the position of only control and sanction into exploring the possible ways for more support. Producers and their organisations have greater expectation for support from the national responsible authorities, not only in terms of marketing, but a real support of local production. One of the option could be to find a way within different national support schemes how to prioritize and/or favour over others those producers that are dedicated to local production with higher added value such as the registered products within the EU Quality Policy. Positive effects will be also on local employment and economy, thus contributing to thriving of rural areas. Special focus should be given in this regard to young generation in order to make this way of lay attractive for them and thus ensure generation exchange in agriculture and food production sectors and keep the rural areas lively. Significant contribution would be to small and medium sized producers and development of rural tourism and agritourism.</p>
6. Vidzeme (Latvia)	<p>Effectiveness of both policy measures will be high towards achieving objectives, though whilst SO3.3.1 can be more seen at national level, M19.21 - at local level. Most of the projects already have been implemented or approved within both policy measures. By the results it can be expected that all indicated outputs and outcomes will be achieved and even exceeded – in SO3.3.1. reaching at least 69% of the total number determined at the national level, new job</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>created - 30%, non-financial investments in enterprises non-material investment and fixed assets - 31%; in M19.21 planned new jobs created will exceed 211 % of nationally planned.</p> <p>However, whilst SO3.3.1 with centralized implementation will exceed all outcomes, it is fairly challenging to evaluate impact of M19.21 on whole region as its local focus and contribution that is targeted on specific group and focused on local needs, decentralized implementation and different interventions can be best evaluated by the compilation of its impact on local areas.</p> <p>Regarding relevance of SO3.3.1, the need of public governments will be addressed by improved public infrastructure that is used by all residents of the municipality, less the benefits for business or employment. M19.2 responds the needs of local SMEs and active citizens, but the strategic need for wider areas and systematic change has not been fully addressed. The long-term impact of the policy measures cannot be assessed as it is still currently under implementation stages.</p> <p>The development and planning phase of both policy measures has been fully aligned with other relevant national measures. Implementation of both measures is monitored and coordinated inter-institutionally, including also bottom-up approach included in both, evermore in M19.21 including also stakeholders from different sectors in decision making processes and throughout the implementation period. However, the coherence of the SO3.3.1 policy measure with regional and local programs is debatable, but M19.2 due to not aligned timelines was not reaching its' possible synergies with SSOs, but having strong synergies with local development programs.</p> <p>To reduce the above-mentioned shortcomings, it would be advisable to ensure and monitor the coherence of the policy measures also during the implementation period. It will facilitate complementarity of SO3.3.1 and M19.2 and ensure not only achievement of objectives of both policies, but also their precise correspondence to defined needs of the pilot region – to develop high value-added products, services and diversification of business. M19.2 and SO3.3.1 provide the necessary preconditions to meet these needs, but more strategic and systematic coordination between VPR and local governments is needed.</p>
7. Hame (Finland)	<p>Overall the policy measure evaluated fulfills its objectives well. Effectiveness and relevance of the measure meet their objectives excellently or well according to 80% of the respondents. Coherence of the measure proved to be more difficult to assess as this requires background information that not all respondents naturally had at the time of the interview.</p> <p>The following is a summary of the most significant conclusions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased co-operation with business advisers, Leader groups and authorities is needed. This need for building of an authority ecosystem has emerged also in the stakeholder panel. This requires clear goals, tasks, information and responsibilities for everyone involved. • Similar approach, similar support opportunities in all Leader groups to make it easy for companies to apply for support (also from different Leader groups). • The inclusion of farm-based enterprises in Leader programs in the case of non-agricultural entrepreneurship. Now funding through ELY-Centre and with an emphasis on big things, this is not fully understood by small actors. • Making project impact assessment easier and more life-like, business-like. It should be noted that investment aid can also have a direct employment effect, for example on construction investments (approx. 80% is spent on wages). The number of people employed is not always a relevant measure, purchasing services can have a bigger impact locally. • Support for digital system deployment for those who are not used to using them. The support approach should be on-going. • Raising the profile of Leader programs, support for ordinary entrepreneurship, advertising, even to improve the performance of some modern top industry.

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
8. Central Greece (Greece)	<p>The overall conclusion of the evaluation survey and interviews indicates that the involved stakeholders consider the implementation and outcomes of the Measure 41 of the LEADER Programme during 2007-2013 to be generally successful to a “Moderate and Great Extent”. The specific questions revealed gaps regarding the bio economy, environmental, ICT and EU policies awareness. It was also highlighted the need for support provision on vulnerable groups.</p> <p>The measure was aimed at existing farmers and didn't promote new entrants getting into farming. New policy initiatives need to provide more schemes with financial rewards for attracting people in rural areas. The measure contributed to achieving the rural policy objectives/package for the region, but not as a whole.</p> <p>Central Greece is the second largest administrative region in Greece in total area, where 5.2% of the country's population is concentrated (Eurostat, 2020). It is a manufacturing hotspot, developed mainly due to its proximity to the region of Attiki. Central Greece is rich in mineral resources and also possesses a developed agricultural sector, a relatively developed tourism infrastructure and a growing services sector. However, the region is characterised by geographical and economic heterogeneity, with urban areas being more developed than the rural and mountainous zones. Within the tertiary sector the most dynamic segments addressing the wholesale and retail trade, transport, accommodation and food service activities. The unemployment rate has been decreasing and in 2019 was at 17.2%% (Eurostat, 2020), as compared to 18.9% in 2018, and a figure significantly lower compared to the 2013 level (28.2%). This represents a total of 40,400 people unemployed. This number positions the region in sixth place for the highest unemployment rate among the 13 Greek regions, slightly below the national average (17.3%) and above the EU28 (6.3%) average (Eurostat, 2020). Rural Attractiveness to entice newcomers to rural areas and create job opportunities in the region is a long-term objective, requiring a combination of policy approaches. These approaches should consider the aforementioned strengths and weaknesses of the region in order to ensure the successful outcome.</p>
9. Flanders (Belgium)	<p>The overall ambitions of the region are to create attractive and sustainable climate resilient productive landscapes, thereby balancing agricultural intensification with environmental concerns and climate resilience. The policy instrument of Rural Development Plans, and more specifically agri-environment-climate management agreements between farmers and the Government of Flanders seems very suitable for realising the overall ambition of the region.</p> <p>European agri-environment-climate measures are based on the common principle that farmers deliver environment-climate services for which society pays. Due to the voluntary nature the issue of farmers' motives or reasons for participation has been an important topic of investigation both from an academic and policy side (Van Herzele et al., 2013). The farmers' rationale for participation in agri-environment-climate management agreements plays against the backdrop of a continued debate over whether to develop relatively simple management agreements that can be readily applied by many farmers or give greater priority to management agreements that are more targeted but are often more complex. The analyses suggest that participation varies with the management agreements' complexity. Engaged participants wish to integrate agri-environment-climate management into the overall farm enterprise, and they are most likely to commit themselves for the long term. The primary recommendation here is to ensure that enough flexibility and entrepreneurship is appropriately fostered and supported.</p> <p>Since the potential for creating landscape attractiveness varies greatly from one location to another, GIS and remote sensing -based tools and could be helpful to farm advisors and farmers in evaluating specific locations against criteria such as management agreement specifications, estimated crop productivity, climate resilience and environmental performance. The ambition formulated is at the interface between the reform of the Common Agricultural Policy, the European green deal and the new strategy for biodiversity. In rural areas, farmers, businesses and</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>communities are particularly affected by the corona pandemic. All of these new policies together with the reliance plan will form the basis for exploring the potential in the forthcoming foresighting analysis.</p>
10. Monaghan (Ireland)	<p>The overall conclusion of the evaluation survey and interviews indicates that the Monaghan stakeholders consider the implementation of the Monaghan LEADER Environmental Theme and outcomes during 2014-2020 to be generally successful to a “Moderate High Extent”, with Effectiveness, Relevance and Coherence, rated 2.8, 3.2 and 3.3 out of 4.0, respectively. While in addressing Monaghan’s specific needs the measure’s implementation was considered “Moderate Low to a Small Extent”, with an overall rating of 1.7/4.0.</p> <p>However the feedback clearly indicates “To a Great Extent” that the needs and objectives currently targeted by the Environmental measures in LEADER still apply at the end of its implementation, and should be extended and made an integral part of Monaghan’s next LEADER Plan. In doing this, there is much to be learned from the feedback in section 3 to input to Monaghan’s policy processes and next LEADER programme and projects.</p> <p>Most stakeholders had clear opinions on the effectiveness of the LEADER Environmental measure in Monaghan and its impact on awareness, renewable energy and employment opportunities. However, they were not as clear on its relevance and coherence with other policies, and its impact on farming financial security, sustainable agriculture, COVID/Brexit and new entrants in Monaghan. Future LEADER and other policy initiatives in Monaghan need to address these issues.</p> <p>As discussed in section 3.7, the Semex Text Mining enabled a large amount of previous work and literature to be analysed to give a different perspective, with interesting insights and very useful sentiment quotes. Overall, the analysis confirms the very rich survey feedback.</p> <p>Common Issues:</p> <p>Regarding the effectiveness of the LEADER Environmental outcomes to date for Monaghan, the stakeholders’ feedback was positive (“moderate high”) with the work of Monaghan Integrated Development (MID) being complemented, with good projects and biodiversity being addressed. However, community awareness of the environmental measure is low and a small budget means small impact. The external factors that contributed to achieving the measures’ objectives included a good emphasis on environmental themes that helped ensure focus, though there is a need for more awareness, training, wider community collaboration and political support.</p> <p>The stakeholders suggested many key success factors and barriers to achieving Environmental impact in Monaghan. These provide excellent detailed issues that will need to be addressed in future policy initiatives. These have been grouped into the following clusters to help future LEADER plans with that.</p> <p>The stakeholders also positively rated the relevance of the LEADER environmental measures in Monaghan to be “Moderate High”. They felt that the county started from a low knowledge base in the community and requires a ground up approach rather than top down. Policies need further development to improve the environment, but environmental measures are now a priority in the CAP, and LEADER can do its part to deliver on this. Significant learning and capacity building continue to be required.</p> <p>The environment remains under threat, loss of biodiversity continues to be an issue. A lot has been done, but there is a lot to do. Environmental measures should continue to be a priority in future policy measures in Monaghan. Environmental measures also represent opportunities for farm diversification, i.e., biomass, biogas, etc. COVID has highlighted the human need for sustainable locally produced foods and a clean environment, cheaper to protect and preserve rather correct the damage. There is a need for educating people in general regarding the environment</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>The stakeholders feedback on the overall coherence of the LEADER Environmental measure in Monaghan was again positive, being “Moderate High” overall, though they indicated a very definite support that environmental measures should be an integral part of the next LEADER Plan. They felt that there is a strong link between identified needs from public consultation running through to the objectives and actions in the LEADER local development strategy.</p> <p>Environmental measures are now a national priority under Ireland’s National Climate Change Action Plan. The LEADER objectives and outcomes are in line with these policies. There are many National and Local agencies working toward improving the environment, so LEADER in Monaghan should focus on small business start-ups, including small farm enterprises.</p> <p>Environmental measures in LEADER are well aligned with CAP. LEADER is now viewed as the vehicle for community-based, bottom-up environmental actions. The protection of the rural environments is critical for the sustainability of rural economies. LEADER works on the ground in communities with real issues. The local community now look to the LEADER programme for inspiration and opportunities for community based environmental actions. However, more clarity is needed with terminology used.</p> <p>Monaghan is a disadvantaged border region, where more investment is needed. The stakeholders hope for more practical projects as training/education increase. While Farmers are willing, they feel that the political will is lacking.</p> <p>Monaghan Specific Issues</p> <p>The feedback from the stakeholders on how the LEADER Environment measures impacted on Monaghan’s needs was lower and more varied. From “a very small extent” in addressing COVID-19/Brexit, to “a small extent” in encouraging new entrants and the financial security of farming, to a “moderate low extent” in rural attractiveness and sustainable agriculture, to “Moderate” for raising awareness and renewable energy. So, there is much to be addressed in new policy measures for Monaghan in the coming years.</p> <p>The stakeholders felt that newcomers are fundamental to farming in future. However current environmental measures are aimed at existing farmers, some new entrants may want to farm for the purpose of protecting biodiversity or creating renewable energy, but they would be very small in number. Current Irish National policy does not promote new entrants, and its very difficult to get into farming in Ireland due to the difficulty in accessing land due to costs. Currently in LEADER the operating rules limit funding of primary production activities in agriculture. This can be a constraining factor due to the broad interpretation of the rules. New policy initiatives need to provide more schemes with financial rewards.</p> <p>A recent initiative is “We Belong - Monaghan’s Migrant Integration Strategy and Action Plan 2020-2023” that was launched on 16th November 2020 . The vision for Monaghan is one that celebrates the diversity of its communities. A county where everyone who lives, works and visits are valued, respected and supported to fully participate and contribute to their communities, and to achieve this goal through collaboration, inter-agency working and promoting values of equality, dignity and inclusion. This includes the involvement of all stakeholders. Immigration is important and has been hit hard by COVID – e.g. crops not harvested due to lack of seasonal migrant labour.</p> <p>The strategy recognises that Monaghan’s local population would be in decline but for migrants coming in. This decline can result in reduced services etc.- a downward spiral. So, migrants can stabilise the population and thus stabilise services for everyone. Future policy measures must aim to boost business and entrepreneurship – targeting local entrepreneurs, people new to farming and entrepreneurs from outside the region.</p> <p>Rural Attractiveness to entice newcomers to a rural Monaghan is a long-term objective, requiring a combination of policy approaches. LEADER environmental measures along with economic development and job creation measures are playing their part in attracting newcomers. Positive</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>environmental measures will be a contributing factor for those wanting to live and work in clean and biodiverse rural areas. If projects follow through from training this can potentially build rural attractiveness, however rural Monaghan policy is behind the curve in promoting locality.</p> <p>The current Environmental measures in LEADER placed a high priority on awareness raising and stakeholders are now seeing a follow through with specific actions, i.e., biodiversity plans from community groups, etc. Especially In areas where projects have been undertaken. However, more needs to be done. There is a need for fundamental education about the environment, and progress monitoring based on the numbers impacted by the projects.</p> <p>Regarding more sustainable agriculture, production of vegetables and forestry development, the stakeholders feel that there is much to be done. While, environmental awareness has perhaps led to small unknown or unmeasured changes in farming practices, small Horticulture producers struggle to find funding, access to the market is blocked for local producers and misplaced planning objections has created a stoppage in felling and re-planting of forests by an unknown number of years and discouraged new interested parties in planting. Economic factors are prioritized. Investments are needed to improve soil quality for vegetable production.</p> <p>Stakeholders felt that more needs to be done through the environmental measures in LEADER to improve the focus on the potential for renewable energy for rural areas. Training and capacity building are key. People must first understand the technology potential for savings. Flowing from this will be project ideas and applications for funding.</p> <p>The feedback indicates that the Environmental outcomes have had little influence on mitigating the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and Brexit uncertainty. While COVID and Brexit could not be anticipated by the 2014/2020 LEADER Programme, a rural area that is environmentally aware could be a driver post-COVID for urban dwellers to take up residence in those rural areas. Biodiversity training will impact on the local community over time making rural areas more attractive. COVID has driven people outdoors and these projects will enhance outdoor spaces. Regarding Brexit, the preparation work to date has been good.</p> <p>While the impact of the environmental outcomes in LEADER to date to increase employment opportunities in Monaghan’s rural areas has been limited, this should increase in future. However, all the current projects have produced employment and there has been significant demand from enterprise project promoters for project funding. Within these funded projects is the potential for significant job creation. Training in environmental areas will enhance and overlap the training received by some in other areas such as heritage/tour guides, and lead to more rural employment in the future.</p>
11. Poland	<p>According to the evaluation study, the planned activities under the local policy instrument successfully achieve their objectives and are still relevant. Due to the local specificity and well-chosen selection criteria, the action has a strong impact on the local economy and community. The promotion of specific activities made it possible to support those ideas which involve the use of local potential and support various social groups, including young women, people bringing up children, the elderly or the disabled.</p> <p>According to the beneficiaries, in the process of applying for support the most positive thing was very substantial assistance from the LAG. Thanks to the measure in question the new entities had a fairly significant impact on the creation of new jobs, which confirmed that the support realised was in line with its intention to support the creation of new jobs in new fields in the local area.</p> <p>As the main obstacles in the process of applying for support beneficiaries pointed out the complexity and huge amount of formalities. Also in the process of applying for support beneficiaries pointed out the complexity and huge amount of formalities, but also technical difficulties resulting the software used for managing the application system. In terms of</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>supporting sources of income for local residents, the measure in question had a moderate, although positive, impact.</p> <p>Interesting is that COVID-19 had some, but usually a limited impact on the functioning of the projects implemented under the measure in question. According to the beneficiaries, COVID inhibited business traffic in many industries which was a problem for the developing start-up so the nature of this impact was mostly related to the external factors.</p> <p>The measure was designed in 2014 but reflects very well the current local, but also global challenges, related to the environmental needs, strengthen the reduction of use of the natural resources or support innovation and new business models.</p>
12. Galilee (Israel)	<p>The Galilee is a region in the periphery with characteristics of “Out of sight out of mind” of the government of Israel. The population is small (therefore not really can have any influence on voting) and is mainly an agricultural region next to the Lebanese border. It is characterised by many municipalities, with mayors concentrating on staying in position, and therefore investing locally rather than having a broad vision for the regions’ needs.</p> <p>The “Leading Team” was composed of people from different sectors that are not “officials” and were selected according to their innovative approach and broad vision. They were asked to look forward to the needs of the Galilee in coming years and how they analyse the development of the Galilee, mainly from economic aspects, how can the Galilee recruit young people from the centre of Israel and convince young people from the Galilee to stay in the region, as well as the wellbeing of the residents regarding health and services.</p> <p>It was agreed by all stakeholders that were involved in the discussions that developing the regions’ potential, finding the new role in the emerging world knowledge-based economy, the Galilee needs to widen its focus and go beyond its own innovation landscape to explore the global and trans-regional dimension to the full. It was accepted by the participants in the workshops that digitalisation infrastructure is a key element in the creation of future economic development of the region, as well as improving wellbeing of the Galilee residents. The Galilee Pilot utilised the work undertaken in previous activities and subsequently the foresight activities to highlight key elements of current needs with a look for the future, and to bring these into the development work for the benefit of the people as well as the different sectors – agriculture, industry, tourism, health and education. The initial development mechanism for presenting the policy measures was done by experienced experts in the different area with knowledge of the Galilee needs.</p> <p>The activity ensured that youngsters are the key beneficiaries of this activities and results, by enabling the influencing of policy makers and, in particular, those that implement RTD policy and allocate financial and other resources across regions. The methodology for the implementation of the plans is based on the essential involvement of SMEs and the success of the process. It was understood by all that the costs we are aiming at are high and therefore the investment needs the PPP – Private Public Partnership approach. The discussions regarding the possibilities to implement those ideas in the future began already with both governmental/parliament people as well as with VC and NGO that has already connection to the Galilee.</p> <p>Therefore we examined the potential future trends in the region’s different sectors and innovation development in the Galilee. The “Leading Team” placed emphasis on: assumed future investment in infrastructure and innovation steps at the regional level will upgrade the Galilee region, and it will have an impact on economic output and future developments in regional economies and will enable young people to have employment at the region and stay with appropriate salaries. The policies of the Israeli government were taken into account, with efforts to make the politicians implement the promises and allocate the budgets needed in the coming years.</p>

Pilot	Conclusions and Recommendations from regional evaluation
	<p>We all realized that the main obstacle to the Galilee development is to find the budget to implement those ideas. We were approaching governmental entities as well as the KKL-JNF that is declaring (Allocation project 2040) they are obliged to bring 500,000 new residents to the Galilee up to 2030.</p> <p>Until now, we have not succeeded to get any defined budget or any commitment for the near future, and we are working hard on this task.</p> <p>Effectiveness: The Galilee region is low performing and digitally inferior to the centre of Israel with regards to the business and public sector, but there is a strong local interest for further improving the efficiency, effectiveness and governance of public services design, public infrastructure and delivery through expanded digitalisation in the region. Summing up the aims, objectives, goals and focus areas of the strategies expressed by the major sectors in Galilee shows that all the sectors have similar main goals, as they all emphasise knowledge development, user-centricity, digital skills, digital security, and need for the further development and digitalisation of the region.</p> <p>Efficiency: By improving the digitalization infrastructure we estimate that outstanding accuracy and the ability to react at speed will prove useful especially for new SMEs and business models that are based on short product lifecycles. The group at MIGAL, which is developing the Corona vaccine, is seeking for greater IT integration for their needs of big data uses, at a faster and more effective reaction time. In the precision agriculture sector, the proliferation of the Internet of Things (IoT) will mean greater interconnectivity and sophistication leading to intelligent algorithms that will bring higher profit to farmers.</p> <p>Relevance: As discussed with many stakeholders from different sectors it seems that the direction chosen by the “Leading Team” is most relevant to most of them. Not all know how it will affect their business, but have the confidence it will upgrade their business as well as bring more young people to choose the Galilee as their home.</p> <p>Coherence: The Galilee actions to bridge the digital divide was design to be comprehensive. Digital technologies should be part of the answer in all Galilee sectors’ development policy while remaining fully in line with the principle of policy coherence for development. The Galilee strategy does precisely this and is therefore very welcome by the “Leading Team”.</p> <p>Key to implementing this action will be to involve all actors, in the different sectors, in the public and in the private sector, both in the civil society and in the scientific community. Only by such an inclusive approach can this approach ensure that the digitalisation process leaves no one behind.</p> <p>Public funding will not be sufficient for a truly transformative digitalisation process. Further funds will need to be leveraged. In this context, the private sector can play an instrumental role through its expertise and its technology and innovation know-how.</p>

Table 11 Conclusions and recommendations of the pilot evaluation report

14 Annex 5: The evaluation matrix

14.1 Introduction

This document presents the evaluation matrix for assessing policies and a step-by-step guide to use it effectively. Its aim is to offer support to the Pilots while they identify and gather the information required for the evaluation process as well as help them to select tools for evidence collection.

The Evaluation Matrix is divided into three sections. The first two sections provide guidelines for collecting the information required for the evaluation, while the third section guides Pilots throughout the evaluation process according to three different criteria: effectiveness, relevance, and coherence.

Section one guides the Pilots in collecting general relevant information on the policy measure:³

- (0) Needs
- (1) Objectives
- (2) Inputs/actions
- (3) Outputs
- (4) Outcomes
- (5) Impacts

Section two guides the Pilots in gathering information on the external factors that influence the policy measure.

- (a) External influencing factors
- (b) External policy factors

In section one and two, the columns of the evaluation matrix provide the following information:

- Description about the information required
- Tools and references that can be used to get this information (documents, surveys, interviews, focus group, etc)
- Suggested questions that can be asked to obtain the required information

Section three guides the Pilots in evaluating the policy while using the information collected in section 1 and 2, according to the following criteria:

- (I) Effectiveness
- (II) Relevance

³ The element from which the policy is implemented, which can be a funding program, a tool/instrument etc.

(III) Coherence

In section three, the columns of the evaluation matrix provide the following information

- Description of the evaluation criteria
- Tools that can be used to make the evaluation
- Evaluation questions

The interactions between these three sections: – evaluation elements, external factors and evaluation criteria – are shown in the diagram below and considered in greater detail in the table that follows it.

Figure 26 Logframe – graphical illustration

It is worth mentioning that the measures that the Pilots will assess are at different stage of implementation. The policy measure selected for evaluation may not be fully implemented while others will be. By using the evaluation matrix Pilots can evaluate the measure in such a way that it can be compared with the other pilots.

A uniform approach is therefore a fundamental requirement.

11.4 Steps to carry out the evaluation process

STEP 1: Pilots select one or two policy measures related to the policy that you have already identified in the deliverable 4.4: needs- policy canvas developed in task 4.4

For the selection of the policy measure, the following criteria shall be taken into account:

- Future Relevance: the policy responds to one or more critical or relevant needs
- Policy Influence: Capacity to steer and monitor the policy measures in this area
- Easy access to required information
- Implementation Status: The policy measure must be completed or in an advanced stage of implementation (80%). It must be ensured that there will be enough information available (qualitative and quantitative) to evaluate it.

STEP 2: Pilot complete the profile of the police measure selected: *the table below will help the pilots to describe the chosen policy measure. The table provides a quick overview of the type of*

policy measure selected and some key aspects that have been considered for its selection. In order to ensure the traceability of the evaluation process, some information about the needs and the pillar defined in the previous deliverables (D1.3 and D4.4) is included in the profile.

Policy Description	
<i>Pillar</i> (according to the rural attractiveness needs D1.3)	<p>Seven main pillars have been set-up for the needs gathering in Task 1.</p> <p>Select the pillar related to the needs of the selected policy measure (see deliverable D1.3)</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Availability of public and other services 2. Recreational and social activities 3. Living conditions and quality of life 4. Demographics and Human capital 5. Business Economy and Innovation 6. Social and cultural aspects of rural areas 7. Environment and biodiversity
Needs	List and describe the needs covered by the selected policy measure. (see the identified needs for this policy measure in D4.4 Policy-needs canvas)
Policy measure/instrument	<p>Title of the policy measure selected and a brief description (half a page maximum, preferably shorter).</p> <p>Explain how the policy instrument is expected to deliver. This can be via investments, subsidies or taxes, but may also work through other mechanisms such as rules and regulations, such as land use restrictions (e.g. on housing; on farming), as well as forms of collaboration in-kind / public-private partnerships</p>
Coordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders involved in the project and beneficiaries (e.g. farmers, local authorities, local businesses, NGO, etc.) • Dissemination: evidence of diffusion and evaluation of results (e.g. telling people about the action via radio, local, regional or national newspapers, free newspapers, websites, social media (e.g. twitter, ..), (town hall) meetings, more academic literature,) and • Monitoring (e.g. measurement of the number of people, frequency of activities, views of)
Budget allocation	<p>Amount of budget allocated to the intervention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU contribution if any • National/regional/local contribution (indicate which. If more than one, indicate the amount for each) • Private funding(e.g. industry, foundation, business angel) • Other funding sources
Policy / administrative capacity needed to steer and monitor the measure	<p>Number of people (FTE⁴)</p> <p>Tools / equipment to roll out the measure</p>

⁴ FTE: Full time equivalent for example two people both working half days only would be the equivalent of one person in FTE

Policy Description	
Beneficiaries	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of beneficiaries (e.g.: SME/farmer/NGO etc.) (if not available, try to make an estimate e.g. 1-10, 11-50, 51-100, Over 100 but less than 1000, over a thousand, etc.) Number of beneficiaries relative to the intended target group(s)(e.g. 50 farmers out of a regional population of, e.g., 500) Type of beneficiaries (SME/farmer/NGO etc.)
Status	Policy measure should be finished or on going but well-advanced: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Start date End date (actual or anticipated) Extent to which the measure is advanced (between 80% and 100% implemented)
Transferability	Is the measure transferable to other areas or to other farms/rural businesses facing the same issue? Is it transferable outside of the farming/rural domain? Has it been already replicated elsewhere in your country or in Europe?
Synergies with other EU policy measures	Does the policy contribute to the objectives of other EU policy domains? (e.g. energy transition, digitalization, circular economy, healthy living, etc.)

Table 12 Template for the regional policy profiles

STEP 3: Pilots collect the information from the different sources following the guidelines of the evaluation matrix in section 1 and 2 (see the table below). Desk research is the fundamental tool and can be complemented surveying panel members and conducting interviews with interested participants. Pilots will decide on the stakeholders, including policy makers, that should be asked for further input. The information will also be completed with the needs identified in the different approaches carried out through text mining.

	What you are looking for	What tools you could use to find the information (examples)	What information you could gather and questions you could ask (examples)
Section 1: Evaluation elements			
(0) Needs (e.g. of society, of stakeholders/beneficiaries)	Description of need for the policy measure – why it is being implemented, what problem or opportunity it aims to address	Desk research (from existing documents e.g. those shared in the regional Hub, and from the data that you are gathering (monitoring data)) D4.4 Policy needs canvas Text mining	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What were the initial needs that the policy measure was designed to address? Has that changed? If so, why? What are the current needs?
(1) Objectives	Description of key objectives of the policy measure.	Desk research (e.g. documents shared in the regional Hub, monitoring data)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What are the objectives of the policy measure?

	What you are looking for	What tools you could use to find the information (examples)	What information you could gather and questions you could ask (examples)
(2) Inputs/actions	Include a description of inputs and actions of the policy measure.	Desk research (e.g. documents from the regional Hub, monitoring data)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What is the budget of the policy measure? What are the actions following the policy measure?
(3) Outputs	Include a description of direct outputs i.e. short-term results of the activities. (affect to all policy measure) about the measures in progress - result so far	Desk research (e.g. documents shared in the regional Hub, monitoring / reporting / evaluation / data)	<p>Quantitative: Indicators will depend on your policy measure but could include numbers of people, activities, products, outputs as well as types of people, activities, products, etc.</p> <p>For example, a tourism-related project could see an increase in the number of reservations.</p>
(4) Outcomes	Include a description of medium-term outcomes achieved.	Desk research e.g. (documents shared in the regional Hub, monitoring data)	<p>Quantitative: Indicators will depend on your policy measure but could include change in behaviour</p> <p>For example, a tourism-related project could record year-on-year increased tourism revenues</p> <p>Also: new jobs, new services, etc., as a result of the measure (in the medium term).</p>
(5) Impacts	<p>Include a description of wider long-term economic, societal, and environmental impacts that have been achieved or are expected to be achieved.</p> <p>Impacts are difficult to determine, especially if a policy measure has been applied only recently</p> <p>(this applies to policy measures that have been running for 4 to 5 year)</p>	<p>Desk research (e.g. documents shared in the regional Hub, monitoring data)</p> <p>Interviews/survey to beneficiaries involved (SME, farmers, associations, NGO, etc)</p>	<p>Quantitative: Indicators (see annex- Impact survey) -</p> <p>For example, a tourism related project could see a number of new facilities starting up as attractions for the increased number of tourists and the economy of the town/region improving</p> <p>Also refers to social development, economic growth, and sustainability.</p> <p>Qualitative information e.g. the tourism project could see visitor satisfaction in a post-visit survey</p>
Section 2: External Factors			
(a) External influencing factors	Include a description of influencing factors that	Focus group with policy makers and/or	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> What have been the external factors influencing the

	What you are looking for	What tools you could use to find the information (examples)	What information you could gather and questions you could ask (examples)
	are external to your policy measure but have a direct impact on it.	Interview/Survey to beneficiaries involved (SME, farmers, associations, NGO, etc)	<p>implementation or achievement of the objectives of the policy measure (external factors are those political, economic, environmental, social or technological factors that have influenced the achievement of the objectives of the policy measure but are beyond the control of the policy measure evaluated)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please include 3 most relevant external factors that have influenced the policy implementation process
(b) External policy factors (outside of the policy area of the measure)	Include a description of other relevant policies (local, regional, national, EU).	Information (D4.4 Policy Needs-Canvas)	<p>There are several policies related to one need (international level, EU level, regional level and local/grassroot level)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A brief description of 3 other policy measures (name of the policy measure, 1-2 sentence description)

Table 13 Evaluation Matrix, part 1

STEP 4: Pilots evaluate the criteria of effectiveness, relevance, and coherence following the guidelines of the evaluation matrix in section 3 (see the table below). It is recommended to organize focus groups with regional stakeholders panel to present and discuss the evaluation results.

	What you are looking for	What tools you could use to find the information (examples)	What information you could gather and questions you could ask (examples)
Section 3: Evaluation criteria			
(l) Effectiveness	Effectiveness - assessment of how successful the action has been in terms of achieving or making progress (see 3 above: Outputs, 4: Outcomes)	<p>Desk research</p> <p>Focus group with policy makers /Survey to beneficiaries involved (SME, farmers, associations, NGO, etc)</p>	Assessment of success in reaching the objectives (1) and achieving the outputs (3) and outcomes (4) of the policy measure and how external factors (a) have possibly contributed to the

	towards the objectives set (see 1 above) and how external factors (see a above) and other external policy factors (see b above) have influenced the progress.		achievement of the objectives (see annex: Effectiveness survey): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent the policy measure has achieved its objectives? Include an evidence-based judgement of the progress made. What were the key success factors in achieving the objectives? What were the key obstacles hindering the progress?
(II) Relevance	Relevance – assessment of the relationship between the needs (e.g. of society) (0) and the objectives (1) of the intervention.	D4.4 Policy needs canvas Interview/Survey to beneficiaries involved (SME, farmers, associations, NGO, etc) and/or policy maker (focus group), Text mining	Assessment of needs (0) and objectives (1) of the policy measure: (see annex- Relevance survey) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent the objectives of the policy measure met the initial needs? How well do the original objectives correspond to the current needs? To what extent the policy measure is still relevant?
(III) Coherence	Coherence – assessment of the initiative (0-3) compared to other initiatives and policies (b).	Desk research D4.4 Policy-needs canvas there are several policies related to one need (international level, EU level, regional level and local/grassroot level).	Assessment of coherence of the policy measure (0-3) with other policy measures (b) (see annex- Coherence survey) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To what extent the policy measure is coherent with other policy interventions which have similar objectives? To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other local and regional policy measures? To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant national policy measures? To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant EU policy measures? CAP, LEADER To what extent the policy measure is contributing to EU added value?(e.g.EU Regions Targets: Globalisation, climate change, Energy challenge, demographic change)

Table 14 Evaluation matrix, part 2

STEP 5: Pilots develop the evaluation report, following the suggested index:**Executive summary****1. Introduction (1-2 pages)**

1.1 Objectives (what measure you are evaluating and why you chose this measure)

1.2 Context of the evaluation (in the context of your project under RIA)

1.3 Structure of the evaluation report (a brief description of the chapters below)

2. Background and status of the policy measure (2-3 pages)

Description of the background of the policy measure and the current status. Including answers to the following questions:

- Why was the policy measure initiated? What was the background context?
- What were the objectives of the measure?
- What is the current status of implementation? How is the progress made? (Is related to how is progress monitoring done?)
- Have there been issues related to the implementation? (e.g. any delays, speeding up, changes in plans, etc.)
- What is the current situation of the different stakeholders targeted by the measure? How have they been affected by the measure?

3. Evaluation of the impacts of the policy measure (5-7 pages)

3.1 Description - Describe the context, needs, objectives, inputs, outputs, outcomes, impacts of the policy measure in a structured manner, supporting and structuring the evaluation. Use the tools above to do this in a structured way.

3.2 Effectiveness of the policy measure

The evaluation of effectiveness is a measure of the progress made towards achieving the objectives of the policy measure, looking for evidence of why, whether or how these changes are attributed to the policy measure. Evaluation questions to be answered in this section includes:

- To what extent the policy measure has achieved its objectives? Include an evidence-based judgement of the progress made.
- What were the key success factors in achieving the objectives?
- What were the key obstacles hindering the progress?

3.3 Relevance of the policy measure

The relevance refers to evaluation of whether the objectives of the policy measure are still relevant or there has been changes in the underlying problems and drivers. The evaluation looks

at the relationship between the needs and problems and the objectives of the policy measure. Questions that should be answered in this section:

- To what extent the objectives of the policy measure met the initial needs?
- How well do the original objectives correspond to the current needs?
- To what extent the policy measure is still relevant?

3.4 Coherence of the policy measure

The evaluation of coherence assesses how well the policy measure is aligned with other local, regional, national or EU policy measures. The evaluation report should provide answers to following questions:

- To what extent is the policy measure coherent with other policy interventions having similar objectives?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with other local and regional policy measures?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant national policy measures?
- To what extent is the policy measure aligned with relevant EU policy measures? E.g. CAP, LEADER, digital transformation, green deal, demographic change, etc.
- To what extent the policy measure is contributing to EU added value? (e.g. EU Regional Targets: Globalisation, climate change, energy challenge, demographic change)

4. Conclusions (1-2 pages)

This chapter summarises your findings from the evaluation of your policy measure. (What are the final conclusions that you draw from the evaluation?)

15 Annex 6: Pilot Evaluation Reports

Due to the file size the reports are included in a zip file as separate documents.

16 Annex 7: Word clouds and bar charts from text mining analysis

16.1 Word cloud

Figure 27 Word cloud Slovakia

Figure 28 Word cloud Poland

Figure 31 Word cloud Italy

Figure 32 Word cloud Israel

16.2 Histograms from Evaluation Reports

Figure 39 Bar chart of Israel

Figure 40 Bar chart of Latvia

Figure 41 Bar chart of Slovakia

Figure 42 Bar chart of Poland

Figure 43 Bar chart of Belgium

Figure 44 Bar chart of Spain

Figure 45 Bar chart of Greece

Figure 46 Bar chart of Italy

Figure 47 Bar chart of Finland

Figure 48 Bar chart of Ireland

Figure 49 Bar chart of North Macedonia

Figure 50 Bar chart of Czech Republic